

D2.4

Data Sharing and Sovereignty Mechanisms

CERTH

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Abstract

This document outlines the status of the data sharing and sovereignty mechanisms. It provides a detailed explanation of the design overview, the applied technologies, the current implementation status, the next steps, and any encountered issues and obstacles for the components related to WP2. Finally, it discusses the established communication channels.

Keywords

Data Sharing, Data Sovereignty

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PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIoD	AI on Demand
API	Application Programming Interface
CES	Credentials Event Service
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CLI	Command Line Interface
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CSVW	CSV on the Web
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DB	Database
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DID	Decentralized Identifier
DIHs	Digital Innovation Hubs
DNS	Domain Name System
DPF	Data Plane Framework
DSP	Data Space Protocol
DSSC	Data Space Support Centre
EC	European Commission
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETL	Extract Transform Load
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GRLC	Git Repository Linked data API Constructor
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IAM	Identity and Access Management
ID	Identifier
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association

JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data
MS	Microsoft
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PDF	Portable Document Format
R2RML	RDB to RDF Mapping Language
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
RML	RDF Mapping Language
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
STA	SensorThings API
TTL	Terse RDF Triple Language
UI	User Interface
URL	Universal Resource Locator
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VC	Verifiable Credential
VP	Verifiable Presentation
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package
WSGI	Web Server Gateway Interface
XLSX	Excel Spreadsheet XML
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language
YARRRML	Yet Another RDF Mapping Language

Executive summary

D2.4 provides a comprehensive overview of the final status of the final status of the components developed under WP2. The deliverable places particular emphasis on the data sharing and the data sovereignty mechanisms within the DATAMITE framework. To provide additional context, references are also made to complementary modules from WP3, including those related to data quality, data governance, support tools, and security

The document presents the adopted technologies, developed tools, and framework extensions, along with the issues encountered, lessons learned, and communication channels established with other European projects. From a technical perspective, it describes the design, interactions, dependencies, and integration status of the WP2 components within the overall framework. From a user perspective, it includes illustrative figures from the DATAMITE user interface, highlighting features related to data sharing and sovereignty.

The focus of this deliverable spans the implementation of data sharing mechanisms and connectors for IDSA dataspace, EU portals, and data markets, the creation of compliant data products, harmonisation processes, and the exploration of data sovereignty research through the integration of dedicated tools.

1 Introduction

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission (EC) as part of the Horizon Europe programme and coordinated by the ITI - Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain framework to improve DATA Monetisation, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetisation potential at two levels. At the internal level, users will have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability), and will be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like Artificial Intelligence (AI).

At the external level, keeping users in control of their data will provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, serving as a facilitator for onboarding SMEs, including low-tech SMEs, into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions will function as a catalyst to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

According to the Grant Agreement this deliverable must describe the development status, applied technologies, communication channels, and any encountered issues and obstacles.

In alignment with these requirements, this document presents the final release of the components developed under WP2. For each, it provides an overview of its design, current implementation status, functional role within the DATAMITE framework, and how it integrates with the other components.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Executive Summary:** Summarises the content and main findings of the document.
- **Section 1 Introduction:** Provides the general context, objectives, dependencies and structure of the deliverable.

- **Section 2 Data Sharing Mechanisms for IDSA Dataspaces:** Describes the design and development status of the IDSA and GAIA-X connectors and components. It also describes the communication channels established with IDSA dataspaces, considered as potential integrated data ecosystems for publishing data through the DATAMITE framework
- **Section 3 Data Sharing Mechanisms for EU Portals and Data Markets:** Explains the implementation of DATAMITE's brokers for a range of EU portals and data markets. It provides a detailed analysis of the integrated data ecosystems, as well as the design, workflow, and architecture of the relevant data-sharing mechanisms.
- **Section 4 DATAMITE's Data Products & Support tools:** Presents the design, development, and management of DATAMITE's data products. In addition, it provides a detailed analysis of the harmonisation processes and supporting tools integrated in the framework.
- **Section 5 Mechanisms for Enhancing Data Sovereignty:** Emphasises the data sovereignty aspects of the framework and the relevant tools. For each tool, it describes its role, design, and integration with the other components.
- **Section 6 Evaluation Guidance for Data Sovereignty:** Provides a review of the state of the art, explains the applied methodology, and presents results related to data sovereignty evaluation.
- **Section 7 User Interface for Data Sharing & Sovereignty:** Includes several figures and descriptions of the user interface associated with the components discussed in this document.
- **Section 8 Conclusions:** Summarises the final status of the components developed under WP2 and their integration
- **Appendix A Data product concept analysis:** Analyses the data product in the context of data spaces.

1.3 Document Dependencies

This document forms part of a series of living deliverables developed throughout the project. The first version, delivered in M18, provided an overview of the WP2 components and outlined the planned development activities. D2.4 constitutes the final document in this series and is scheduled for delivery in M33.

2 Data sharing mechanisms for IDSA Dataspaces

One of the objectives of the DATAMITE project is to help companies share data securely and efficiently by providing tools to build their own data products, define their own data sharing policies and share their data products in interoperable data spaces.

For the development of its data-sharing modules, DATAMITE adopted the EDC¹ (Eclipse dataspace components), which are aligned with both IDSA and Gaia-X frameworks. The GAIA-X Data Product and the onboarding modules were also integrated into the architecture to support trust mechanisms.

This section presents the communication channels and collaborations established with other Horizon Europe energy-sector projects (Section 2.1), and the design and implementation details of the IDSA and GAIA-X connectors and components (Section 2.2).

2.1 Communication channels

As previously noted in deliverable D2.2, strategic collaborations were established with energy-sector projects implementing data spaces, with the objective of enhancing pilot operations via reliable data exchange mechanisms.

IDSA invited Sonia Jimenez (IDSA), the Energy Interoperability Task Force lead, to the Task 2.1 call on Feb 13, 2025, to introduce the work ongoing by the task force towards interoperability in data spaces. She presented the paper on Interoperability Framework in Energy Data Spaces.

As a follow-up, the DATAMITE partners also participated in an all-day workshop of the Energy Interoperability Task Force projects on March 5, 2025, hosted by the OMEGA-X project. The workshop focused on demonstrating the technical and semantic interoperability between the 5 energy projects, funded by the European Commission to set the grounds for a common European Energy Data Space, coordinated by the CSA Int:net². This was a good opportunity to learn about and discuss challenges, potential solutions and best practices for achieving interoperability in data spaces.

¹ Eclipse Dataspace Components (github.com)

² <https://intnet.eu/>

In parallel, links with three energy data space projects (EDDIE, DATA CELLAR and OMEGA-X) were established. Technical investigations were carried out by the project team to explore which energy data spaces could be feasible to interact with, for the data space-related scenarios in DATAMITE's energy pilots.

- EDDIE was excluded from further collaboration, as the project does not implement the IDS and GAIA-X concepts required for interoperability with DATAMITE.
- DATA CELLAR enables the establishment of a data space within the energy sector, contributing to the expansion of networks across local energy communities in the EU. It features a dedicated onboarding mechanism, supported by a custom-developed identity extension. With support from members of the DATA CELLAR project the connector in both consumer and provider roles were deployed as well as a thorough review of its implementation was conducted. The DATAMITE EDC connector relies on Keycloak³ as its identity manager, which inherently prevents interoperability with DATA CELLAR connector that uses its own EDC extension for identity management.
- OMEGA-X presented a similar situation as with the DATA CELLAR project; however, in this case, the lack of interoperability stemmed from the different data space connector versions used. In DATAMITE, a significantly more recent version was implemented, making compatibility between the two connectors unfeasible. However, DATAMITE was successfully integrated with the OMEGA-X Clearing House after receiving a valid certificate from one of its Trust Anchors. Once the Clearing House API URLs were updated, the Gaia-X module functioned seamlessly without any issues. Despite successful onboarding, actual data exchange could not occur due to version mismatches in the EDC core connector components used by the two projects.

At the time of writing, the DATAMITE project team continues to explore potential workarounds to address interoperability limitations when interacting with the Energy dataspaces. All these interoperability issues can be avoided in the future with the widespread adoption of the Dataspace Protocol and other specifications such as the Decentralised Claims protocol⁴.

³ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

⁴ <https://github.com/eclipse-dataspace-dcp/decentralized-claims-protocol>

2.2 IDSA & GAIA-X Connectors and Components

As illustrated in Figure 1 (from the deliverable *D1.4 Requirements and Architecture (M30)*), the “IDSA & GAIA-X connectors and Components”) form a central part of the Data Sharing Module. This functionality is primarily implemented through:

- The EDC connector (EDC v0.10.1), extended with modules developed within DATAMITE, and,
- The Gaia-X (TAGUS version) component.

Together, these components are directly linked to the Data Product Composition component. They enable internal data products to be published through the EDC connector, making them consumable by other EDC-compliant connectors. Additionally, they support the publication of the internal product as a Gaia-X compliant data product, ready to be consumed through a Gaia-X catalog.

Figure 1. IDSA & GAIA-X connectors & components Architecture in M30

2.2.1 Eclipse Dataspace Components

The Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) project is an open-source initiative under the Eclipse Foundation, which provides a modular framework for organisations to manage and share data. In today's data-driven world, the ability to securely exchange information while maintaining data sovereignty and privacy is paramount. EDC addresses this need by providing a robust framework

of modular, interoperable, and extensible components that facilitate the creation and management of data spaces.

Central to the EDC framework is the Dataspace Protocol (DSP), which standardises the interactions between different data spaces and their components. DSP enables seamless communication and data exchange across various systems, enhancing interoperability and facilitating collaboration among organisations. This protocol allows for the secure transfer of data while ensuring that data ownership and usage rights are respected, thereby reinforcing trust among participants in the data ecosystem.

The architecture of EDC is based on a decentralised approach, which means that data can be shared without the need for a central repository, thereby reducing the risk of data breaches and enhancing control over data assets. Key features of EDC include comprehensive data governance capabilities, flexible access control mechanisms, and support for various data types and sources, making it an adaptable solution for diverse industries.

Moreover, EDC promotes interoperability between different data spaces, enabling organisations to collaborate across boundaries and leverage external data sources effectively. By facilitating secure data exchange, organisations can unlock new opportunities for innovation, analytics, and insights while ensuring compliance with regulatory frameworks such as GDPR.

DATAMITE, as a forward-thinking entity, utilises these EDC components and the Dataspace Protocol to actively participate in data spaces, enabling seamless data acquisition and sharing while adhering to best practices in data management and privacy. Through the EDC framework, DATAMITE is positioned to enhance its data strategies and drive value from its data assets in a secure and efficient manner. By engaging with the EDC community, DATAMITE also contributes to the ongoing development and enhancement of these components, ensuring that they evolve in line with the latest technological advancements and industry needs.

2.2.1.1 Design Overview

The EDC Connector is a dual-component system designed to facilitate data sharing and transfer, comprising the Control Plane and Data Plane, shown in Figure 2. This architecture aligns with EDC's modular design philosophy, allowing for deployment either as a single monolith (for simple use cases) or as clusters of individual services. It is advisable to keep the Control Plane and Data Plane separate to enable independent management and scaling.

The Control Plane plays a crucial role in establishing contract agreements that regulate data access, overseeing data transfers, and ensuring compliance with usage policies. For instance,

when a data consumer's Control Plane seeks to access data, it initiates a contract negotiation with the data provider's connector. This negotiation occurs asynchronously and culminates in a contract agreement upon approval. Subsequently, the consumer connector leverages this agreement to commence data transfers with the provider connector. These transfers may either be one-off (finite) transactions or ongoing (non-finite) data streams. The provider Control Plane has the capability to pause, resume, or terminate these transfers based on specific conditions, such as the expiration of a contract agreement.

On the other hand, the Data Plane is tasked with executing the actual data transfers as directed by the Control Plane. It employs specialised technologies, including messaging systems or data integration platforms, to facilitate this process. EDC provides the Data Plane Framework (DPF) for the development of custom Data Planes. Alternatively, organisations can create Data Planes using various programming languages or technologies and integrate them with the EDC Control Plane by implementing the Data Plane Signalling API.

Figure 2. Connector Base Architecture and Communication Flow

2.2.1.2 Final Status

The DATAMITE EDC Connector repository on GitLab serves as the final implementation baseline for secure and interoperable data sharing within WP2. It aligns with the Gaia-X initiative and

adheres to IDSA standards, facilitating seamless interaction between data ecosystems while ensuring compliance, security, and efficient data flow.

Architecture and Core Functionalities

The architecture of the DATAMITE EDC Connector is structured to support various data exchange scenarios through a modular and extensible design. It separates the Control Plane, which manages contract agreements and policy enforcement, from the Data Plane, responsible for the actual data transfer. This separation allows for independent scaling and management of both planes, promoting a microservices approach that enhances flexibility and maintainability.

In terms of data transfer mechanisms, the connector supports asynchronous data transfers, enabling data consumers to initiate requests without waiting for immediate responses. This capability is crucial for handling large datasets and streaming data. Additionally, the connector utilises an event-driven architecture, allowing it to respond to various triggers and events, which facilitates real-time data processing and transfer.

Extensibility and Integration

The connector's integration with the EDC framework ensures compliance with IDSA standards, which facilitates adherence to data usage policies and compliance requirements, including data provenance and audit trails. By implementing Gaia-X principles, it enhances interoperability across data spaces while preserving data sovereignty through standardised interfaces.

Data usage policy management is crucial; the Control Plane oversees compliance with data access requests, enabling real-time evaluations and contract negotiations between data providers and consumers for automated data sharing agreements.

The repository includes extensibility features, allowing developers to create custom connectors tailored to specific data sources or business needs. It also provides APIs for seamless integration with external systems, promoting efficient data exchange.

Monitoring and Compliance

The connector features robust logging and monitoring capabilities, allowing stakeholders to track data transfers, ensure compliance, and analyse performance metrics essential for data integrity and security. Its eventing system automatically sends logs to external logging tools, enhancing the observability of data activities within the dataspace.

Stable Deployment

The provided Docker Compose file configures a multi-container application for the DATAMITE project's data sharing environment, incorporating both provider and consumer services, along with essential infrastructure elements like databases and secret management systems.

Central to the setup are two control planes: the provider-control plane and consumer-control plane, each running in its own container and built from specified Dockerfiles. They connect to their respective PostgreSQL databases, which are initialised with environment variables for username, password, and database name, and mount local volumes for data persistence.

The control planes manage data sharing agreements and ensure compliance with usage policies, exposing multiple ports for APIs related to data management and validation, enabling communication with external clients and services.

Complementing the control planes are the data plane components: provider-data plane and consumer-data plane. These services also use Dockerfiles and expose HTTP and public APIs, handling efficient and secure data transfers.

Key to the architecture are the provider-vault and consumer-vault services utilising HashiCorp's Vault for secret management. These vaults include health checks and expose APIs for secure secret storage, with local directory mounts for persistence.

Additionally, a DNS host resolver service facilitates name resolution for containers, enhancing inter-service communication. All services connect through a common network named `datamite-dataspaces-network`.

Overall, this Docker Compose configuration provides a robust foundation for a data sharing platform, integrating components for efficient, secure, and compliant data handling, embodying a microservices architecture that is easily deployable and manageable with Docker.

Future Directions

The DATAMITE project aims to continually enhance the EDC Connector. Improvements that have not yet been implemented but could be addressed include: advanced analytics using machine learning to analyse data usage patterns and optimize approval processes, as well as improved security features with advanced encryption and access control for secure data transmission. Expanding compatibility with additional data sources and platforms will also increase the connector's utility.

In conclusion, the DATAMITE EDC Connector repository is a robust solution for improving data sharing in line with modern standards. Its modular architecture, compliance with IDSA and Gaia-X, and extensive functionalities make it vital for organisations seeking effective data utilisation while ensuring security and compliance. Future advancements are expected to reinforce its position in the data integration landscape.

2.2.2 GAIA-X Data Product & Onboarding module

To participate in a Gaia-X compliant data space, a company should follow a certification process that starts with the definition and certification of the company itself and the data products it offers. A data product is an asset exchanged between providers and potential consumers. To capture the attention of potential consumers, it is essential to begin by precisely defining that data product. A more detailed analysis of the data product concept in the context of data spaces is included in Appendix C: Data product concept analysis. The DATAMITE data product includes the metadata necessary to describe it as a service within the Gaia-X ecosystem.

DATAMITE will offer a framework that allows the company to define and create that Gaia-X compliant data product. A DATAMITE data product is considered a collection of data resources offered by a legal or natural entity. Each resource offered by the data product is exposed through an access point where properties such as the URL where that resource will be available are specified.

The DATAMITE Gaia-X onboarding process defined, is a crucial step during which verifiable credentials are created for all participants: the legal entity, the data product provider, and the product itself. The product is then transformed into a Gaia-X service offering. This meticulous process ensures that all aspects are precisely defined, thoroughly documented, and ready for consumption. In essence, Gaia-X's ecosystem consists of participants and service offerings that adhere to the requirements outlined in the Gaia-X Trust Framework.

2.2.2.1 Design Overview

To define and provide a data product in a Gaia-X dataspace, the following steps have been defined:

1. Define an API that encapsulates the data product.
2. Create the asset in the EDC, including the ODRL (Open Digital Rights Language) policies.
3. Generate the Gaia-X self-description of the data product:

- a) Automatically extract the fields of the self-description already included in the EDC asset model.
 - b) Add the missing information via a Graphical User Interface (GUI)
4. Follow the compliance process to get the verifiable credentials and verifiable presentation from the Gaia-X compliance service.
 5. Publish the data product in the Credentials Event Service (CES)

To facilitate and automate the process of onboarding, a module has been defined under the “IDSA Gaia-X Connectors and Components” folder in the DATAMITE Eclipse Gitlab, the “Gaia-X Data product Onboarding Ces Publishing”⁵ module.

The objectives of this module are:

- Helping companies in fulfilling the technical prerequisites needed to participate in a Gaia-X data space.
- Prepare the information the Gaia-X model needs to follow the compliance process for participants and data products.
- Design, implement and deploy an API to facilitate (and automate as much as possible) the Gaia-X self-descriptors generation, compliance and publish processes.

2.2.2.2 Final Status

Figure 3 presents the APIs defined and implemented, detailing their respective functionalities. These APIs were successfully tested using the current development Tagus version 1 of the Gaia-X Clearing House, confirming their compliance with Gaia-X requirements.

⁵ Eclipse Research Labs / DATAMITE project / data-sharing / IDSA Gaia-X Connectors and Components / GaiaX Dataproduct Onboarding Ces Publishing · GitLab

DATAMITE 0.1.0 OAS 3.1
/openapi.json
Datamite API documentation

Datamite External API

POST	/createWebDID	Create Did	Create the company DID
POST	/createLegalParticipant	Createlegalparticipant	Create Legal Participant for the company
POST	/createDataProduct	Createdataproducitwithresources	Create DataProduct
POST	/createAndPublishDataProduct	Createandpublishdataproducit	Create and publish data product
POST	/callToCompliance	Calltocompliance	Call to compliance service of Gaia-X
POST	/callToCredentialsEventService	Calltocredentialseventservice	Call to Credential Event Service of Gaia-X
GET	/getDataProductsList	Getdataproducitlist	Get DataProduct lists
GET	/getDataProduct	Getdataproducitbyname	Get data product given its name
GET	/getCESRecords	Getcesrecords	Get CES registries published

Figure 3. DATAMITE Gaia-X Data Product Onboarding & Ces Publishing API

In addition to the APIs above, which enable any organisation meeting Gaia-X prerequisites to define descriptors and publish services, DATAMITE has also implemented dedicated APIs for publishing internal data products to Gaia-X. These are presented in Figure 4.

Datamite internal data product

GET	/export-dataproduct-composition-to-gaiax	Exporttogaiaxmodel
POST	/publish-dataproduct-internal	Createandpublishdataproducit

Figure 4. DATAMITE Gaia-X Data product Onboarding & Ces Publishing API for internal data product

POST /export-data-product-composition-to-gaiax

This API converts the metadata of an internal DATAMITE data product (identified by UUID) into the format required for Gaia-X publication.

POST /publish-dataproduct-internal

Once the first API has generated the correct format, the second one handles its publication.

Both APIs are executed sequentially from within the framework. If some of the properties are missing from the internal data product, users complete the information through a frontend interface and then click the publish button.

Both the generic APIs and the onboarding APIs have been integrated with the logging-tool. This component records all interactions made with the API and provides dedicated endpoints for monitoring API calls as illustrated in Figure 5. The logging tool has prepared a series of endpoints for this purpose, as shown in Figure 5, and these are the ones that have been used in each of the endpoints.

GAIA-X Operations related to GAIA-X	
POST	<code>/gaiaxlogs/createdid</code> To log information when a domain is created
POST	<code>/gaiaxlogs/createParticipant</code> To log information when a participant is created
POST	<code>/gaiaxlogs/publishDataProduct</code> To log information when a data product is published
POST	<code>/gaiaxlogs/exportGaiaxModel</code> To log information when a model is exported
GET	<code>/gaiaxlogs/searchWithFilters</code> Filters the GaiaX logs by the below fields, empty the values from fields not desired, each filter is applied with and operator

Figure 5. DATAMITE logging tool API for Gaia-X

2.2.2.3 Lessons learnt and open issues

Gaia-X has defined a technological framework to follow the onboarding process. However, this framework has evolved during the project. Furthermore, there are several independent initiatives that are defining and developing modules and technologies that should interoperate, including IDSA and the Eclipse Data Spaces Components group among others.

The future development and convergence efforts of these initiatives will be paramount to facilitate the deployment of interoperable data spaces and even the whole dataspace concept adoption. The following lessons learnt and open issues were identified during WP2 development.

GAIA-X clearinghouse versions ([Specifications](#))

Currently, two different versions of the Gaia-X clearinghouse coexist (TAGUS and LOIRE), and a new one is planned in a few months (DANUBE).

The LOIRE implementation introduces important changes from the previous version, including the Verifiable Credential model.

The participant model has changed, and LOIRE Gaia-X Compliance is designed using a set of core principles, starting from the Standard Compliance scheme, which is refined in the Label schemes. However, the labels are mainly for infrastructure (cloud) services, and there are a few defined regarding data products.

DATAMITE has based the onboarding on the TAGUS version since LOIRE has become mature recently. Future implementations of DATAMITE should update the compliance module to the latest clearinghouse version.

Integration of the onboarding process with the dataspace authentication, authorisation and policy enforcement.

The onboarding process is a set of Verifiable credentials (VCs), which should be used for authentication, authorisation and policy definition and enforcement processes within the dataspace. However, these processes are not yet fully integrated across the rest of the modules handling data transfer, logging, and publish/search functionalities. In addition, the definition of two competing protocols for Verifiable Credentials exchange and verification is a challenge for interoperability. These two protocols are the Eclipse Dataspace Decentralised Claims Protocol ([Eclipse Dataspace Decentralised Claims Protocol | projects.eclipse.org](https://projects.eclipse.org)) and “OpenID for Verifiable Credentials” ([OpenID for Verifiable Credentials - OpenID Foundation](https://openid.org)).

Participant and data product and service models

The Gaia-X models for participant and data products mismatch the EDC internal models. This gap complicates the translation of assets and policies between the two ecosystems.

Future developments of the “Gaia-x Data product Onboarding CES Publishing” module, will address this by:

- Implementing translation from the EDC Asset and Contract definition models to Gaia-X data compliant data product descriptors. The next figures (Figure 6 and Figure 7) show the information included in the EDC models: Asset and Contract definition model.

Figure 6. EDC Connector Asset model interface

Figure 7. EDC Connector Contract definition model interface

- Including an EDC connector URL and Asset ID in the service offering description instead of the public API.

These improvements will enable the EDC data product deployment to connect tighter with the GAIA-X data product self-description.

3 Data Sharing Mechanisms for EU Portals and Data Markets

The data brokering service⁶ is implemented as a Python Flask application, designed to provide a unified interface for publishing dataset metadata to various European data portals. The service is developed within the broader context of the DATAMITE framework, which integrates tools and services supporting data ingestion, transformation, profiling, quality assessment, and publication. While other components of DATAMITE manage data ingestion and the creation of structured data products, the focus of this service is the publication of metadata to external portals in a controlled and standardised manner.

3.1 Unified Design

The service is built using the Flask-RESTX extension, which facilitates the definition of REST APIs and automatically generates Open API-compliant Swagger documentation. This design choice ensures that the service provides a well-defined, self-documented interface for interacting with the underlying publication logic.

Figure 8. Architecture of the brokering service based on a plugin/extension schema

⁶ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/brokers-eu-portals>

Internally, the service adheres to a plugin-based architecture as shown in Figure 8. Each supported European portal is associated with a dedicated plugin that encapsulates the translation logic, metadata schema, and publication procedures specific to that portal.

This design provides extensibility: adding support for a new portal requires only the implementation of a new plugin, following the prescribed structure. At service start-up, all available plugins are dynamically registered, validated, and made available through the unified API.

The brokering service interacts with other components of DATAMITE, particularly the Data Products Service. The Data Products Service produces entities referred to as data products, which are structured collections of datasets and artefacts accompanied by metadata and a public URL. The metadata publication service retrieves the metadata associated with a data product, translates it to the schema of the target EU portal, and executes the publication through the portal's dedicated API.

Auth Operations related to the authorization. Only for testing.		^
POST	/api/login Authorizes user to the datamite platform	∨
GET	/api/{plugin_name}/token API calls related to the login of the EU portal	∨
General Operations related to all registered data brokers.		^
GET	/api/brokers Returns the registered data brokers	∨ 🔒
GET	/api/health	∨
GET	/api/publications API calls related to the publications	∨ 🔒
Data Products Operations related to the data product metadata.		^
GET	/api/{plugin_name}/metadata API calls related to the data product metadata	∨ 🔒
GET	/api/{plugin_name}/schema API calls related to the schema of the EU portal	∨ 🔒
Publications Operations related to the data product publications.		^
DELETE	/api/{plugin_name}/publication Deletes publication from the EU portal	∨ 🔒
GET	/api/{plugin_name}/publication Gets publication from the EU portal	∨ 🔒
POST	/api/{plugin_name}/publication Adds publications to the EU portal	∨ 🔒
PUT	/api/{plugin_name}/publication Edits publications to the EU portal	∨ 🔒

Figure 9. The API of the brokering service

The service exposes a single, unified API for managing metadata publication across all supported European data portals. This API is organised into several endpoints, which abstract away the

portal-specific details and provide a consistent interface, as shown in Figure 9. The main endpoints are grouped as follows:

Service-level endpoints

- **/api/brokers (GET):** Returns the list of supported EU portals. Each portal corresponds to a plugin located in the plugin folder. During service initialisation, plugins are validated and registered; successfully registered plugins appear in the returned list.
- **/api/health (GET):** Provides a health check of the service. Returns HTTP 200 if the service is running.
- **/api/publications (GET):** Retrieves the list of previously published data products. Metadata is not stored in full within the service; instead, a minimal record is maintained in the external Atlas DB service. This record includes identifiers such as the publication ID, the associated portal, the identifier assigned by the portal, and timestamps for creation and modification.

Metadata endpoints

- **/api/{plugin_name}/metadata (GET):** Retrieves the metadata of a given data product from the Data Products Service. The metadata is then translated into the target portal's schema (e.g., AI-on-Demand, CKAN-based portals). Missing or unmapped fields are returned as blank values. This endpoint allows the user to review and complete the metadata before final publication.
- **/api/{plugin_name}/schema (GET):** Returns the JSON schema required by the target portal. For each plugin, the schema is provided as part of its configuration, along with a mapping file that defines the correspondence between data product fields and portal fields.

Publication endpoints (CRUD)

- **/api/{plugin_name}/publication (POST):** Publishes the completed metadata to the target EU portal. This operation corresponds to the Create step of the CRUD cycle.
- **/api/{plugin_name}/publication (PUT):** Updates an existing publication in the target EU portal (Update operation).
- **/api/{plugin_name}/publication (DELETE):** Deletes a previously published entry from the target portal (Delete operation).
- **/api/{plugin_name}/publication (GET):** Retrieves a previously published metadata record from the portal (Read operation).

This API design abstracts the complexity of portal-specific APIs, ensures that each portal can be supported by a dedicated plugin, while the core service exposes a uniform set of endpoints to the user following the CRUD model.

Metadata translation and validation

A central function of the service is the translation of metadata between the internal schema of DATAMITE data products and the external schemas required by EU portals. This is achieved using a mapping.json file that accompanies each plugin. This file specifies field-level correspondences between the source schema (data product) and the target schema (portal). The service uses this mapping to automatically construct a translated metadata entity in JSON format. To ensure compliance with portal requirements, the service also incorporates JSON schema validation. Each metadata entity produced during translation is validated against the schema defined by the target portal. This validation step ensures that required fields are present, data types are respected, and constraints are met before attempting publication.

Shared libraries and logging

The unified codebase provides common libraries that are reused across plugins, including:

- Metadata translation utilities to apply mapping rules consistently across portals,
- Validation utilities for enforcing JSON schema compliance,
- Logging utilities, which handle local logging of warnings, errors, and informational messages.

This logging mechanism is distinct from the central logging service of the DATAMITE framework, but provides sufficient traceability for debugging and operational monitoring at the service level.

In summary, the unified design of the metadata publication service provides a consistent, extensible, and standards-compliant framework for publishing metadata to a variety of European data portals. By abstracting portal-specific complexities behind a standardised API, the service ensures interoperability and ease of use while maintaining strict adherence to portal requirements through schema validation. The plugin-based architecture facilitates the addition of new portals without modifications to the core codebase, while the common libraries and logging mechanisms provide robustness and maintainability. Together, these design choices make the service a reliable component of the DATAMITE framework, dedicated to ensuring that data products created within the ecosystem are effectively translated, validated, and published in accordance with European data portal standards.

3.2 Integration with DATAMITE services

The brokering service is designed as an integral part of the DATAMITE framework, and its functionality depends on seamless interaction with several other internal services. These connections ensure that metadata publication is aligned with the lifecycle of data products, is properly governed, logged, and secured, and that the published records provide accessible links to underlying artefacts.

The main connected services to the brokering service are the Data Product Composition Service, the Data Governance Service (Atlas DB), the Logging Service, the Access Control Service, and the MinIO storage service.

Figure 10 illustrates the overall design and shows how the brokering service is positioned at the centre of these interactions while acting as the gateway to external European data portals.

Figure 10. The Brokers within the DATAMITE's Architecture

- Service: Manages the list of data products created in the DATAMITE framework. Each data product is defined as a collection of datasets or artefacts, enriched with metadata (e.g., descriptive attributes, quality indicators). The brokering service retrieves the metadata of a given data product through an internal API call, using the product identifier provided by the DATAMITE frontend. Retrieved metadata is validated against the JSON schema for data products maintained in the unified codebase of the brokering service. Only valid metadata is considered for translation and publication to an external portal.

- Data Governance Service (Apache Atlas DB): Serves as the central metadata governance database of DATAMITE. Rather than storing full metadata of published products, the brokering service records structured publication summaries. This record contains identifiers and attributes such as the publication ID, the target platform, the internal product ID, the identifier of the publication in the external portal, the version, and creation and modification timestamps. An example entry is shown in Figure 11.

```
{
  "id": "rKKW6uqbXhKgkaNgsdKNM8HdY7k5aqejVRVeoZNUgoHvXQnB5jHNaxr9YZLJ4G",
  "platform": "AI on Demand",
  "platform_id": "1",
  "title": "Example Publication",
  "description": "A short description of the publication",
  "product_id": "jakwbhavcyuasuyvawhsbda",
  "portal_id": "164",
  "version": 1,
  "created": "2025-03-27T14:49:01Z",
  "modified": "2025-03-27T14:49:01Z"
}
```

Figure 11. The example of a publication entry

When publication is created, updated, or deleted, the brokering service updates Atlas DB through an internal API. The DATAMITE frontend subsequently queries the brokering service API to retrieve publication information, which is returned from Atlas DB. This mechanism guarantees that every publication is tracked and consistently linked to its governance record.

In addition to governance, the framework requires traceability of interactions with external portals. For this purpose, the brokering service is connected to the central Logging Service.

- Logging Service: Captures each time the brokering service executes a Create, Read, Update, or Delete (CRUD) operation on an external portal. The outcome is logged together with contextual information such as the product identifier, the target platform, the performed action, the result status, and a timestamp. These logs provide auditable records of all external interactions and can be used for monitoring and error analysis.
- Access Control Service (Keycloak): All communications with the brokering service are protected by the DATAMITE access control mechanism, which is based on Keycloak and implements role-based access control. Users authenticate through the frontend and obtain a bearer token that is required for every API call to the brokering service. Authorisation is enforced by verifying that the user holds the correct role to perform the requested action. In addition to framework-level authentication, some European data portals require their own

credentials for CRUD operations. The brokering service addresses this by allowing users to supply portal-specific tokens, which are stored temporarily and included in the API requests as an X-API-Key header. The Swagger documentation of the brokering service includes test API calls for both types of authentication: one for the DATAMITE token and one for a portal-specific token. To execute these test calls, users must provide valid credentials with the appropriate roles.

- **MinIO Object Storage:** Provides object storage within the DATAMITE framework. MinIO is responsible for generating open-access links to files or artefacts associated with data products. These links are embedded into the metadata published to external portals, ensuring that the metadata includes direct references to accessible resources. This connection ensures that published records are not only descriptive but also actionable, as users can directly retrieve the underlying files through the provided links.

Taken together, these integrations form the backbone of the brokering service's role in the DATAMITE framework. By connecting to the Data Product Composition Service for metadata retrieval, Atlas DB for governance, the Logging Service for traceability, Keycloak for secure access, and MinIO for artefact accessibility, the brokering service is able to provide a complete, controlled, and transparent publication process. This design guarantees that data products are consistently represented and governed within the framework, while at the same time being made visible to the wider European data ecosystem through standardised publication to external portals.

3.3 Plugins/Portals

3.3.1 AI on Demand (AIoD)

The AI on Demand Platform was launched in January 2019 as part of the AI4EU⁷ consortium, supported by the European Commission under the H2020 programme. Its main purpose is to establish a European Artificial Intelligence On-Demand Platform and Ecosystem, enabling collaboration across all European actors in AI from scientists and entrepreneurs to SMEs, industries, funding bodies, and citizens. The platform offers access to high-level AI services, research expertise, reusable AI components, datasets, and computing resources. It also fosters innovation through industry-led pilots, cascade funding schemes for SMEs and start-ups, and

⁷ <https://www.ai4europe.eu/>

targeted research in key AI domains such as Explainable AI, Physical AI, Verifiable AI, Collaborative AI, and Integrative AI. In addition, the platform supports European Ethical Observatory to ensure adherence to ethical, legal, and socio-economic standards.

For the integration of this portal into our brokering service, we provide three essential files that ensure smooth communication and interoperability between the data product schema and the AI on Demand portal schema:

- `schema.json`: This file⁸ represents the metadata structure, in a json schema format, required by the AI on Demand platform.
- `mapping.json`: This file defines the exact field mappings between DATAMITE's data product schema and the AIoD' schema, ensuring accurate translation of metadata. The connections of the metadata can be found in Figure 12.

Figure 12. DATAMITE's data product to AI on Demand mapping graph of the metadata

⁸<https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/brokers-eu-portals/-/blob/develop/app/plugins/aiod/schema.json>

- `plugin.py`: This file contains monkey-patched⁹ versions of the customized CRUD functions for publication, enabling direct interaction with the AIoD API. It also includes a patched version of the function that handles additional manual mapping rules, which cannot be implemented solely through the `mapping.json` approach.

3.3.2 Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN)

CKAN is the world's leading open-source data portal platform, designed to make it easy to publish, share, and work with data. As a powerful data management system, CKAN provides a robust platform for cataloging, storing, and accessing datasets. It features a rich user-facing interface, a comprehensive API for both data and catalogue management, and built-in tools for data visualisation and exploration. While CKAN itself is not an EU portal, it plays an important role in the European data ecosystem: through the Italian Mistral portal, which is based on CKAN, datasets can be published directly to `data.europa.eu`, the official European Data Portal. This connection ensures that datasets managed and published via CKAN become part of the broader European Open Data infrastructure.

For the integration of this portal into our brokering service, we provide three essential files that enable interoperability and smooth publication of datasets through the CKAN infrastructure:

- `schema.json` This file¹⁰ represents the metadata structure, in a json schema format, required by the CKAN-based portals, ensuring compatibility with the target publication environment.
- `mapping.json`: This file defines the precise mappings between our data product schema and the CKAN schema, enabling a seamless transformation of metadata fields. The connections of the metadata can be found in Figure 13.

⁹ The practice of altering or extending the behavior of a module or class during program execution by re-binding attributes or methods.

¹⁰<https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/brokers-eu-portals/-/blob/develop/app/plugins/ckan/schema.json>

Figure 13. DATAMITE's data product to CKAN mapping graph of the metadata

- `plugin.py`: This file contains monkey-patched versions of the four customised CRUD functions for dataset publication, supporting direct interaction with CKAN APIs. It also includes a patched version of the function that implements additional manual mapping rules, which cannot be expressed using only the `mapping.json` mechanism.

3.3.3 Zenodo

Zenodo¹¹ is an open-access repository, developed under the European OpenAIRE¹² programme and operated by CERN. It provides researchers, institutions, and projects with a trusted platform

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

for publishing, preserving, and sharing datasets, software, publications, and other research outputs. As part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem, Zenodo plays a critical role in making research products FAIR and ensuring their long-term availability through integration with services such as DataCite for persistent identifiers (DOIs).

The Zenodo API¹³ demands a multi-step workflow for record creation and publication. Each record must include both the mandatory metadata and at least one associated file (e.g., datasets, documentation, or software artifacts). This workflow introduces additional complexity, as metadata submission and file upload are tightly coupled and must be orchestrated in sequence. The plugins framework developed in DATAMITE is sufficiently flexible to allow for different custom backends under the same unified API.

The Zenodo plugin is defined through the following files/content in the official repository¹⁴ :

- `schema.json`: Defines the metadata structure required by Zenodo, specifying the attributes that constitute a valid Zenodo record.
- `mapping.json`: Contains the crosswalk between DATAMITE's data product schema and the Zenodo schema, ensuring that all relevant attributes are correctly transformed.
- `plugin.py`: Provides monkey-patched versions of the CRUD functions tailored to Zenodo's API, enabling the creation, update, and publication of records. It also handles specific manual mapping rules that cannot be implemented solely via 'mapping.json'.
- `configuration.py`: Sets the fundamental configuration parameters for the Zenodo backend, such as API endpoints (development vs. production), authentication tokens, and default attributes.

Through this approach, the Zenodo integration follows the same design principles as the AIOD and CKAN plugins: schema alignment, mapping translation, and custom API interaction. Zenodo ensures the trusted preservation and citation of research products, making it an indispensable broker endpoint for scientific dissemination.

¹³ <https://developers.zenodo.org/#rest-api>

¹⁴ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/brokers-eu-portals/-/tree/develop/app/plugins>

3.3.4 Others

3.3.4.1 EOSC metadata harvester

The EOSC harvester was not implemented because EOSC infrastructure became unavailable after the start of the project due to the end of EOSC Future and the start of the following EOSC Beyond project.

The goal of this component was to broadcast DATAMITE data products to a European-wide catalogue and to contribute to the current European efforts of normalising FAIR data.

Equivalent coverage is achieved indirectly via Zenodo (harvested by OpenAIRE in the EOSC Node), and CKAN/Mistral (harvested by dati.gov.it and data.europa.eu).

3.3.4.2 Pontus-X

[Pontus-X](#) is a decentralised digital ecosystem that enables secure, interoperable, and compliant data sharing, AI services, and monetisation across diverse industries and organisations in Europe. It is built on the Gaia-X framework and is powered by Oasis Network's privacy-preserving blockchain. It allows sharing and monetising not only data but also services.

Integration with Pontus-X ecosystem is facilitated thanks to [deltaDAO's nautilus library](#). Nautilus is a TypeScript data economy toolkit allowing building accessible decentralised data pipelines. Due to language differences - nautilus utilising Typescript and broker utilising Python - the Pontus-X implementation of the data sharing broker plugin required some adjustments. The implementation retains the structure of the generic data-sharing broker and its Python implementation of the relevant endpoints. A subprocess Python module is used to delegate the execution of communication with Pontus-X to the nautilus TypeScript code, passing all the relevant configuration and parameters required for a proper integration with the Pontus-X instance. Necessary configuration includes:

- *config.ts* - Containing configuration of the available Pontus-X networks, including token and wallet definition, and
- *.env* – Containing a private wallet key.

The codes for the Pontus-X broker are available on GitLab¹⁵.

¹⁵ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/brokers-pontusx>

4 DATAMITE's Data Products & Support Tools

This section introduces the tools that support the creation and management of data products, which are key building blocks of data spaces and enablers of data sharing with EU Portals and data markets. Transforming raw datasets into well-structured, interoperable, and high-quality data products is essential for secure sharing, reusability, and value creation. Two complementary mechanisms are presented: Data Product Composition and Data Harmonisation, which together improve the usability and consistency of data across domains.

These mechanisms enable participants to make data comparable, support better decision-making, and ensure compliance with interoperability requirements such as those defined by IDSA data spaces, EU Portals, and data markets. Without them, data would remain fragmented and difficult to integrate, limiting its value and trustworthiness.

The Data Product Composition Tool helps users merge, filter, and transform multiple datasets into one coherent data product. It supports aggregation, column and row editing, format conversion, and metadata management. The result is a reusable, compliant output that can be shared, stored, or commercialised.

The Data Harmonisation Tools and Pipelines address heterogeneity issues by aligning datasets with common models and ontologies.

Through interactive graphical interfaces and semantic technologies, these tools ensure compatibility across sources, support automated transformations into knowledge graphs, and facilitate the publication of harmonised datasets in line with linked data best practices.

The following subsections describe in detail the design, implementation, and current status of both mechanisms. Their combined role demonstrates how the DATAMITE framework operationalises the creation of reliable, interoperable, and high-quality data products that uphold the principles of trust, usability, and sovereignty within data spaces.

4.1 Data Product Composition

The Data Product Composition tool, part of DATAMITE's Data Sharing Module, as illustrated in Figure 14, is responsible for transforming one or more input datasets into a single coherent data product by comparing the rows/columns or deleting/retaining specific columns.

The current status of development will be described, including functionalities and Open API (Swagger) documentation. Additionally, the technologies applied in the project will be specified, highlighting their roles and contributions.

Figure 14. The Data Product in DATAMITE's architecture

4.1.1 Design Overview

This section describes the process that users must follow to use the Data Product Composition Tool and the scope of this tool within the DATAMITE framework.

In general, a data product is a specialised output created using data by leveraging data analysis and processing to provide valuable insights and information to users. As a result, the expected output is a data product that is valuable enough to be shared or sold. Figure 15 illustrates the architecture of the Data Product Composition Tool and briefly explains how the tool works.

Figure 15. Data Product Composition tool workflow

The user has the option to import one or multiple datasets via the utilisation of the Data Product Composition tab of the DATAMITE framework. Then, the user can choose which sub-tools of data composition tool they would like to use. The user can choose tools between “analyse”, “aggregate by columns”, “aggregate by rows”, “aggregate by primary key”, “combine into a zip file”, “filter”, “delete” and “retain specific columns”. All sub-tools are interrelated. For example, if the user deletes a column from a dataset, then they will be able to retain another column from the created dataset of the deletion module. Also, the tool interacts with Data Support tools. For example, when the user takes the data product dataset will be able to check the anonymity of this dataset. Finally, the tool can store in a database the data product which was created from the modules and will be available for download by the user.

4.1.2 Final Status

The Data Product Composition Tool is fully implemented in Python, using widely adopted libraries to implement the majority of functions, such as the io library¹⁶, pandas library¹⁷, flask library¹⁸, etc. To support integration with the DATAMITE front-end, the tool is documented using Open API (Swagger), which specifies its available endpoints and facilitates testing. The corresponding repository¹⁹ is maintained under the Eclipse GitLab instance.

The development status of the Data Product Composition Tool can be summarised as follows:

- The data product is stored in DATAMITE and is available for use through the data sharing mechanisms.
- The Data Product Composition Tool is integrated with the front-end environment of DATAMITE.
- The tool also supports other formats e.g. JSON, PARQUET, GeoJSON and PDF files in addition to CSV and XLSX formats for the imported datasets.
- Users are able to insert a series of datasets in different formats like PARQUET, CSV, XLSX and JSON, and after processing, the output will be a data product.
- The format of the output is defined either as a default or as a user's choice. The user is able to choose between CSV, XLSX, JSON and ZIP format of the output data product.
- The DATAMITE's Data Sharing Mechanisms compliant data products and the relevant processes for compliance are examined²⁰ and implemented.
- Functionality is added to allow users to extract a specific subpart of a dataset.
- The data product quality evaluation is explored and defined.
- The data product's metadata are explored and defined.
- The tool also supports anonymisation and deanonymisation features for the output data product.

¹⁶ <https://docs.python.org/3/library/io.html>

¹⁷ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

¹⁸ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/3.0.x/>

¹⁹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/data-product-composition>

²⁰ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

- Support of comparing two or more datasets by primary key and merging them into one dataset if certain criteria are met. The endpoint combine the datasets based on a shared key, creating a unified data product.
- Support of combining two or more datasets into a zipped data product.
- Users are able to save a data product, update data and metadata, search for specific metadata and delete a specific data product
- Users are able to upload one or multiple data products from the database and aggregate them, delete or retain specific columns, extract a specific subpart, combine them into a zip file and update or search metadata.

The integration of the platform ensures that metadata is seamlessly connected with the data governance module, enabling consistent management and compliance across all data assets. Through this integration, the creation of a data product automatically triggers the pipeline responsible for assessing and monitoring data quality. Furthermore, the support tools are able to leverage these data products to perform advanced processing tasks such as anonymisation, harmonisation, or evaluating the fairness and potential biases within the data. This integrated approach provides a holistic ecosystem where governance, quality, and responsible data usage are tightly interconnected.

Figure 16 presents the Swagger documentation for Data Product Composition Tool.

Load data product Everything about load process of data product ^

- POST** /upload_dataset Upload dataset(s) (csv, xlsx and json formats support) v
- GET** /load_data_product Get and load data product by unique ID or file name v

Retrieve data product Everything about retrieve process of data product ^

- GET** /retrieve_data_product Get data product by unique ID or file name v

Data Product Info Analyze dataset/s ^

- POST** /analyze_datasets Analyze datasets v

Aggregate data by primary key Merge datasets by primary key ^

- GET** /show_datasets Show imported and filtered (if filter module was used) files with columns v
- POST** /merge_datasets_byPrimaryKey Merge datasets by primary key v
- GET** /download_merged_dataset_byPrimaryKey Download merged dataset v

Aggregate data by columns Merge datasets by columns ^

- GET** /show_datasets Show imported and filtered (if filter module was used) files with columns v
- POST** /merge_datasets_bycolumns Merge datasets by columns v
- GET** /download_merged_dataset_bycolumns Download merged dataset v

Aggregate data by rows Merge datasets by rows ^

- GET** /show_datasets Show imported and filtered (if filter module was used) files with columns v
- POST** /merge_datasets_byrows Merge datasets by rows v
- GET** /download_merged_dataset_byrows Download merged dataset v

Delete specific columns Delete columns from one or multiple datasets ^

- GET** /get_all_datasets Show all files and the columns v
- POST** /delete_columns Delete specific columns v
- GET** /download_deleted_dataset Download deleted dataset v

Figure 16. SWAGGER Documentation for the Data Product Composition tool

The Open API (SWAGGER) documentation is a front-end environment where the user or the developer will be able to test all the endpoints of the tool to see if the backend interacts well with the front-end. It includes GET and POST requests depending on the action the user wants to perform.

4.2 Data Harmonisation

For data harmonisation purposes, two different and potentially complementary solutions have been developed within DATAMITE: the Data Harmonisation Tools and the Data Harmonisation Pipelines.

The first solution addresses a subset of heterogeneity issues in the description of CSV datasets (e.g., variations in field names and values). These issues can be resolved through a graphical user interface designed for non-technical users.

The second solution targets more complex heterogeneity challenges, where data providers and semantic web experts collaborate to specify the mappings using technologies such as OWL and RML.

These two slightly different approaches can co-exist: mapping rules specified in the GUI tools can be automatically expressed in RML, enabling reuse across both solutions.

4.2.1 Design Overview

4.2.1.1 Data Harmonisation Process and Software Tools

The Data Harmonisation Process is supported by three software tools that enable users to: (i) analyse the given dataset for harmonisation purposes, (ii) bridge the gaps between the parameters of the existing data model (source model) and the new one (target model), and (iii) transform the initial dataset into a new dataset based on the elements defined in the target model.

The Data Harmonisation Process and the three developed software tools have been described in detail in D2.2. In brief, the Metadata Extraction Tool automatically generates a summary of the data contained in the given dataset, including field names and distinct values. The Metadata Mapping Tool (aka Ontology Alignment Tool) provides an interactive graphical user interface that enables users to specify mappings between elements of the source and target models, including both fields (parameters) and their distinct values. Finally, the Data Transformation Tool automatically expresses the initial dataset using the elements defined in the target model, based solely on the specified mapping rules.

The interaction among the three software tools relies on widely used data interchange formats and languages, as well as DATAMITE-specific data structures. More specifically, the dataset should be provided as a CSV file (or as an MS Excel file containing a single sheet), while the source and target data models should be represented as OWL ontologies. For convenience, these

models may also be provided in an MS Excel file with a predefined data structure, allowing them to be automatically transformed into OWL ontologies and further processed by the Metadata Mapping Tool. The specified mapping rules can be expressed in various formats, including, but not limited to, JSON, XML, and YARRRML, each serving different purposes. For example, the JSON format is used by the Data Transformation Tool to automatically represent the initial dataset according to the elements of the target model. Mapping rules expressed in YARRRML can also be automatically transformed into RML and used by the Data Harmonisation Pipelines (described in a separate subsection).

Table 1 summarises the inputs and outputs of each of the three data harmonisation software tools.

Software Tool	Input	Output
Metadata Extraction	Input: A CSV file (or an MS Excel file containing a single sheet).	Output: A new MS Excel file with a predefined data structure.
Metadata Mapping	Input: Source and target models in OWL format (or in the predefined MS Excel format).	Output: Mapping rules specified in various formats, including JSON, XML, HTML and YARRRML.
Data Transformation	Input: A CSV file with the given dataset (or an MS Excel file containing a single sheet) and a JSON file with the specified mapping rules.	Output: A CSV file (or an MS Excel file containing a single sheet) with the harmonised dataset.

Table 1. The input and output of the three Data Harmonisation Tools

From a technical perspective, the tools are accessible via a web application with a unified graphical interface (Figure 17). Users can: (a) provide a dataset and automatically extract metadata by pressing the relevant button, (b) upload the source and target models in order to specify and export mapping rules through a highly interactive GUI, and (c) provide the initial dataset together with the specified mapping rules to automatically generate the harmonised dataset.

Figure 17. The Web Application with the three Data Harmonisation Tools

4.2.1.2 Data Harmonisation Pipelines

The Data Harmonisation Pipelines are based on the adoption of Linked Data and knowledge graph technologies. They implement and execute Linked Data pipelines as depicted in Figure 18, which carry out various general tasks, following the best practices and guidelines of Linked Data publication. These tasks include:

- i. Collecting input datasets from heterogeneous sources (shapefiles, GeoJSON, CSV, relational databases, RESTful APIs) (step 1 in Fig. 20)
- ii. Curate and/or pre-process the datasets when needed (step 2)
- iii. Select and/or create/extend the vocabularies (e.g. ontologies) for the representation of data in a semantic format (step 3)
- iv. Process and transform the datasets into RDF triples in a knowledge graph according to underlying ontologies (step 4)
- v. Perform any necessary post-processing operations on the RDF data (step 4)
- vi. Identify links with other datasets (step 4), and
- vii. Publish the generated datasets as Linked Data and apply the required access control mechanisms (step 4)

As illustrated in the diagram, the Data Harmonisation Pipelines approach considers two complementary approaches: i) data upgrade or semantic up-lifting (step 2a), when data is physically transformed into the target model and stored in a triple store as knowledge graphs (e.g., when data is available as CSV, relational database dumps, shapefiles, etc.); ii) query translation (step 2b), which allows evaluating semantic queries over a virtual RDF dataset, where the original dataset remains in its original source (e.g., relational database, REST APIs).

Moreover, the Data Harmonisation Pipelines approach includes the mechanisms to access the harmonised data. These include not only endpoints for semantic querying (step 5) or navigation of the linked data but also APIs (custom and/or standard-based) as well as Web user interfaces (step 6). This ensure that harmonised datasets can be exploited by other DATAMITE components supporting data analysis, visualisation, and decision support components (step 7).

The final goal of the Data Harmonisation Pipelines is to support the automation of the data harmonisation process as much as possible, minimising or avoiding the need for user interaction. This would allow, for example, the execution of the data harmonisation process automatically whenever new data becomes available (e.g., programmatically via a REST API call or by invoking a CLI job which can be executed even in HPC environments), or to reuse existing pipelines and adapt them to other datasets with minimal user input.

Figure 18. Data harmonisation pipelines

4.2.1.3 Connection between User Interactive Tools and Data Harmonisation Pipelines

One of the tasks in the data harmonisation process concerns the creation of the mapping specification. This is typically a one-time task for one or multiple datasets with similar structures. The Data Harmonisation Pipelines support mappings provided in different formats, including RML (the RDF Mapping Language standard), SPARQL queries (for CSV files), CSVW (for CSV files), and YAML files. For YAML, the mapping can be represented according to a simple pipeline-

specific structure²¹ or according to YARRRML, a human readable text-based representation for declarative Linked Data generation rules that can be used to represent R2RML and RML rules.

In some cases, mapping files can be generated (semi-)automatically. Users may need to manually adjust these automatically generated mappings to ensure alignment with the target ontology. The Data Harmonisation Pipelines also provide a simple user interface to generate YAML mapping files. However, one of the strengths of the Ontology Mapping Tool is its rich and flexible graphical interface GUI for creating mappings.

In particular, two tools can be used: the Metadata Extraction Tool, which creates an ontological representation of an existing data source schema, and the Ontology Alignment/Mapping Tool, which allows users to map these elements accordingly to the ones specified in the target model.

Once the mapping has been created through the user interface, it can be exported in one of the formats supported by the Data Harmonisation Pipelines. The pipelines can then be executed repeatedly in the future (e.g. for example, when new data in the source becomes available).

In the latest version, the Ontology Alignment/Mapping Tool also supports generated mapping as a YARRRML file, ensuring compatibility with the Data Harmonisation Pipelines.

4.2.2 Final Status

4.2.2.1 Data Harmonisation Tools

The Web Application integrating the three Data Harmonisation Tools has been designed to operate either as a stand-alone application or in conjunction with the other components of the DATAMITE framework. Both scenarios are described in detail in the following paragraphs.

Figure 19 presents the initial page of the developed Web Application (aka Home Page), through which users can log in to the DATAMITE platform (if required) and access the three Data Harmonisation Tools.

²¹<https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-support-tools/psnc-data-harmonization-tools#33-general-mapping-generator>

Figure 19. Data Harmonisation Tools – Web Application – Home Page

The Web Application enables registered DATAMITE users to log in to the platform and thereby access not only the three Data Harmonisation Tools, but also the full range of functionality offered by the other DATAMITE software components and the datasets already available within the platform.

In this respect, two distinct usage scenarios can be identified. In the first scenario, the Web Application operates in stand-alone mode, allowing the user to employ the Data Harmonisation Tools independently of the wider DATAMITE infrastructure. In the second scenario, the user can take advantage of the Web Application’s full integration with the DATAMITE ecosystem. These two cases are detailed below.

Case 1: Data Harmonisation as a stand-alone software tool

In this case, the user intends to use the Data Harmonisation Tools as a stand-alone component. This mode is particularly useful for users who wish to perform harmonisation tasks locally without requiring access to additional platform resources or integration with other services. Therefore, the user does not have to log in to the DATAMITE platform, and, as a result, must upload the relevant files manually at each step of the process. The steps are as follows:

(i) Metadata Extraction: The user uploads the dataset (e.g., an MS Excel file) through the interface (Figure 20). The system automatically extracts the metadata and makes it available for download (Figure 21).

Figure 20. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – Metadata Extraction from Uploaded Dataset

Figure 21. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – Downloading automatically extracted Metadata

(ii) Metadata Mapping: The user uploads both the source model (automatically extracted or a revised metadata) and the target model (with the expected data structure and terminology) (Figure 22). This allows the user to specify and export the mapping rules in the desired format (Figure 23).

Figure 22. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – Uploading Source and Target Models

Figure 23. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – Downloading specified Mapping Rules
 (iii) Data Transformation: The user uploads both the initial dataset and the downloaded mapping rules, so that the system can automatically generate the harmonised data (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – Uploading Data and Mapping Rules for Data Transformation

Case 2: Data Harmonisation integrated with the rest components of the DATAMITE platform

In this case, the user intends to use the Data Harmonisation Tools in conjunction with the other components of the DATAMITE platform to harmonise datasets already available in the DATAMITE repositories. In this mode, the Data Harmonisation Tools can interact seamlessly with other DATAMITE components through the respective REST services, ensuring interoperability, reusability of datasets, and enhanced functionality.

If not already logged in, the user must initially log in to the DATAMITE platform using the link provided in the top-right corner (Figure 21) and then follow these steps to perform the harmonisation process.

(i) Metadata Extraction: The user first selects the appropriate file from the DATAMITE repository (Figure 25 and Figure 26). Then, the user clicks “Extract Metadata” and the system automatically extracts the metadata (Figure 27).

Figure 25. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – File Selection for Metadata Extraction (1/2)

Figure 26. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – File Selection for Metadata Extraction (2/2)

Figure 27. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – Metadata Extraction from Selected File

(ii) Metadata Mapping: The user can then proceed to the mapping process by uploading the source and target models and specifying the mapping rules. The defined mapping rules can be downloaded in the appropriate format so that they can be used for data transformation.

(iii) Data Transformation: The user selects the dataset following a process similar to the one described above for metadata extraction and provides the previously specified mapping rules (Figure 28). The harmonised data can then be uploaded to the DATAMITE repository, enabling the user to proceed with its publication.

Figure 28. Web Application for Data Harmonisation purposes – Uploading Harmonised dataset to DATAMITE

4.2.2.2 Data Harmonisation Pipelines

The data harmonisation pipelines include three main components: a CLI tool, a Web Service and a Web-based Graphical User Interface (GUI).

CLI Tool

The CLI tool is an ETL (Extract–Transform–Load) software developed in Python. It integrates existing software components for specific tasks, implements missing functionalities, and connects them transparently into executable pipelines that can be executed via a single interface

The project is distributed with a Dockerfile and a Singularity definition file, which enables the deployment and usage of the pipelines in HPC environments. The code is released under the MIT licence and is available via the GitLab²² repository.

The previous update on the tool, described in D2.3, included:

- Extended and improved support for YAML mappings
 - Support for JSON-LD contexts and/or dictionaries to associate terms with the target ontology/vocabulary
 - Support for multiple levels of property chains

²² <https://gitlab.pcass.pl/daisd-public/dpi-pipelines/pipelines>

- Support for multiple instances of the same property for the same entity
- Support for CSVW mapping specifications
 - Alternative route for semantic lifting CSV inputs
 - Same interface as other pipelines, so it requires an input file and JSON mapping
- Support for NetCDF
 - Treated similarly as CSV input files
- Improved overall performance

The latest version includes:

- Broader YAML support, including the support for YARRRML, which provides a human-readable text-based representation (in YAML) for declarative Linked Data generation rules (e.g., RML).
- Extended set of pre-processing functions (e.g., to enable the transformation of coordinate systems, add an enumerator field in JSON files).
- Extended set of post-processing functions (e.g., to remove unwanted characters or change characters as needed).
- Improved transformation to RDF turtle format (TTL) of the post-processed dataset
- Integration of the latest version of the underlying mapper tool that includes better support for RML functions
- General improvements, e.g., remove folder with initial data in the results directory, adjusting mapping generator for shapefiles to create a single mapping for multiple inputs, improved support for NetCDF files, and bug fixes.

All future work identified in the previous deliverable has been carried out (and beyond), except for the implementation of functions for transformations in mappings in YAML, which has been superseded by YARRRML support. YARRRML allows the specification of functions in YAML, and thus, a custom implementation is no longer needed.

Web Service

The Web Service wraps the CLI tool and exposes its functionalities through a RESTful API. The source code is available in the DATAMITE repository²³.

²³ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-support-tools/psnc-data-harmonization-service>

The latest architecture of the service is illustrated in Figure 29, each box in the diagram is numbered and represents a PaaS container executing a software component, while detailed information on the individual components can be found in the service [confluence](#) page. The service is deployed in a PaaS environment and is available in development and production instances. Each instance provides its own SWAGGER interface for interactive documentation and testing.

- [Production service](#)
- [Production Swagger](#)
- [Development service](#)
- [Development Swagger](#)

Figure 29. Data Harmonisation Pipelines Service architecture

The previous update of the Data Harmonisation Service, described in D2.3, included:

- An update of the REST API aligned with the latest changes in the CLI tool,
- An additional validation of input values,
- An increase of resources in PaaS to handle larger datasets, and
- Deployment of the production instance.

The latest update includes:

- An update of the REST API according to the latest changes in the CLI tool,
- Support for storing the generated harmonised data in an external S3 service bucket;
- Support to transform the generated data into different formats before storing to the S3 bucket,
- Support for merging external RDF graphs into the generated data before storing to the S3 bucket, including support for JSON-LD framing before storing to the S3 bucket
- Integrating of an Elastic Search server for the indexing pipelines and jobs,
- Generation of documentation according to DATAMITE guidelines, and
- Addition of the required files to comply with the CI guidelines in DATAMITE.

These changes cover and extend the future work proposed in the previous deliverable.

As shown in Figure 29, the interfaces provide access to the harmonised data, including a Web-based GUI (box 10 in Figure 29), a customised GRLC service (box 11), and a SensorThings (STA) generation service (box 12), which are described below.

Web-based GUI

The Web-based GUI provides a simple yet complete client graphical user interface (GUI) enabling direct interaction with the DPI service. It enables listing and searching the available pipelines and execution jobs, registering new users and logging in, creating, editing, deleting or executing pipelines (for logged users), as well as creating and editing mapping specifications in YAML (for logged users). A screenshot of the GUI landing page, where the list of DATAMITE pipelines is depicted in Figure 30 and Figure 31, respectively. The GUI is available [online](#), and its source code is available in the DATAMITE [repository](#).

The previous update of the Web-based GUI, described in D2.3 included:

- Improved GUI to facilitate user interaction;
- Integration with KeyCloak;
- Interface for the specification of mappings, which generates the YAML file.

The latest update includes:

- Redesign and implementation of DATAMITE (LOBA) layout styles and components;
- new landing page;
- Extended the options available to users to support the latest functionalities in the Web service;
- improved searching and pagination of pipelines

Customised GRLC service

GRLC is a 3rd party service that enables access to Linked Data via RESTful APIs created on the fly from SPARQL queries. The deployed [service](#) is a customised version of GRLC, including extensions to enable the specification of page number and page size, additional field specification, and more. During the last period, this service was not further extended.

SensorThings API (STA) generation service

The STA generation service provides access to harmonised Linked Data (e.g., stored in Virtuoso triplestore) about observations via a standard OGC SensorThings API. The API is generated automatically from the specified datasets in a triplestore (identified as graphs). The service is deployed in a PaaS environment and is available in development and in production instances:

- [Development](#)
- [Production](#)

The previous update of the STA generation, described in D2.3 included:

- improved performance;
- support for multiple modelling patterns of measurements/observations (as simple observations or as observation collections, including simple results or complex results);
- support for filter parameter (geospatial filters);
- support for user-provided SPARQL endpoint to access harmonised data

The latest update includes:

- further improvements in performance;
- extended the filters supported by the STA generation service;
- possibility to generate non-public endpoints integrated with KeyCloak;

Additionally, in this period the data harmonisation pipelines have been used to carry out the harmonisation of data in DATAMITE. In particular, they were used with the PSNC pilot data.

Figure 30: Data Harmonisation Pipelines Web-based GUI – landing page

Figure 31: Data Harmonisation Pipelines Web-based GUI – list datamite pipelines

5 Mechanisms for Enhancing Data Sovereignty

This section focuses on the concept of data sovereignty, which is a fundamental prerequisite for the creation of trustworthy, secure, and value-generating data spaces. In an environment where data increasingly flows across organisational and national boundaries, sovereignty provides the necessary guarantees that each participant retains control over their data. This control extends to the ways data is stored, accessed, and shared, thereby safeguarding both individual rights and collective interests. Establishing sovereignty is therefore a critical requirement for ensuring compliance with legal frameworks, maintaining trust between actors, and enabling responsible data-driven innovation.

Within the DATAMITE framework, data sovereignty directly supports the “sovereignty and trust” pillar of the data space architecture. This pillar provides the capabilities for participants to identify themselves, define rules governing the use of their data, and ensure that these rules are enforced across different transactions. Without such mechanisms, data sharing would risk becoming opaque, insecure, or non-compliant, thereby limiting both adoption and impact. By embedding sovereignty into the technical infrastructure, the framework ensures that trust and transparency remain integral parts of all exchanges.

The mechanisms presented in this section are designed to put these principles into practice. First, the Policy Library simplifies the creation of machine-readable usage policies, lowering barriers for data providers to express their requirements in a standardised way. Second, the Policy Engine operationalises these requirements by evaluating and enforcing policies throughout contract negotiation and data transfer processes. Third, the Logging Tool provides a robust means of recording and auditing all transactions, thereby ensuring accountability, traceability, and regulatory compliance. Together, these mechanisms reinforce sovereignty by combining preventive, corrective, and monitoring functions.

This section illustrates how data sovereignty can be effectively embedded into operational workflows, strengthening trust, protecting rights, and enabling secure collaboration within the DATAMITE ecosystem and beyond. The design overview and the status of each mechanism are presented in the following subsections.

5.1 Policy Library

The Policy Library enables users to create usage policies for automated enforcement of data usage contracts in the EDC and Gaia-X contexts. It is a backend service accessed through the DATAMITE frontend, simplifying the creation of machine-readable Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) policies. These policies are then made available by the frontend to the Policy Engine for evaluation. The Policy Engine itself is implemented as part of the DATAMITE connector as described in chapter 5.2. The key objective of the Policy Library is to provide a no-code method for data providers to create usage policies for their data products, lowering the bar for proper data sovereignty.

5.1.1 Design Overview

Technically, the Policy Library is a single-endpoint API service used only by the DATAMITE frontend. The high-level concept is, as illustrated in Figure 32, that users specify dynamic parameters required by the policy in the frontend. These get sent to the Policy Library, which populates a set of policy templates (implemented as Python classes) with these parameters and returns the complete policy as a JSON object. Finally, the frontend uploads the policy as part of a contract definition to the EDC management API, from where the Policy Engine can fetch and evaluate it as needed.

Figure 32. High-level overview of DATAMITE policy management in the EDC context

The Policy Library backend service implements the ODRL standard using a hierarchical set of templates written as Python classes. As shown in Figure 33, the policy creation functionality is accessed through a FastAPI application layer. Based on the parameters provided by user, the service infers the structure of the required policy, populates the correct templates with the parameters and renders the final policy document, returning it as a JSON object.

Figure 33. Architecture of the Policy Library backend service

The source code and documentation for the Policy Library are maintained in the DATAMITE GitLab²⁴.

²⁴ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-security/policy-library>

5.1.2 Final Status

For the final release of the Policy Library, support for permission and prohibition rules has been implemented. Users may constrain their rules in the following three ways:

- Time
- Location
- Purpose of use

For example, a user may permit the use of their data product for the year 2025. They would only specify the rule type (“Permission”), along with the lower bound (2025-01-01) and upper bound (2025-12-31) in the frontend. The Policy Library backend service then processes these parameters, creates the exact EDC-compliant ODRL policy, and returns it to the frontend for uploading to the EDC management API.

5.2 Policy Engine

5.2.1 Design Overview

The EDC provides two frameworks to define and enforce policies applicable to the data transaction, from the contract negotiation to the data transfer process.

- **Policy engine:** manages access control in the provider connector
- **Policy monitor:** continuously enforces policy monitoring in streaming scenarios

However, the approach of the EDC is providing the framework to define policies but not implement specific policies, as it is stated in the documentation: *“Following the approach taken with Dataspace Protocol, the core EDC project will not implement specific usage policies. It is expected that usage policy implementations will be provided by other projects and dataspace.”*²⁵

5.2.1.1 Policy Engine

The next sections present the current status of the policy engine framework provided by the EDC.

²⁵<https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/tree/main/docs/developer/ids-dataspace-protocol#dataspace-protocol-architecture>

5.2.1.1.1 Coding required to register policies

The Policy Engine allows the registration of constraint functions. The documentation about the policy engine²⁶ and the registration of a new constraint²⁷ is included in the EDC GitHub.

Some examples of constraint policies can be found in the EDC GitHub, such as:

- The absolute spatial position constraint function²⁸
- The partner-level constraint function²⁹.

However, to register a new policy, coding is required. The Policy Engine, by default, has not registered any policy constraints.

5.2.1.1.2 Provider-side access policies

According to the EDC documentation³⁰, “*contract definitions are how assets and policies are linked together. Those conditions are comprised of a contract policy and an access policy*”

- **Access Policy:** *determines whether a particular consumer is offered an asset or not.*
- **Contract Policy:** *determines the conditions for initiating a contract negotiation for a particular asset. Note that it does not automatically guarantee the successful creation of a contract; it merely expresses the eligibility to start the negotiation.*³¹”

The Policy Engine is executed only on the provider side of the EDC connector.

When registering a constraint function, it is possible to specify the policy scope. Information about policy scope is available in the EDC documentation^{32 33}:

A policy scope defines the context in which a policy is to be evaluated. The EDC provides a fixed set of pre-defined scopes, and it is not possible to add or extend them. The currently available scopes are explained in Table 2.

²⁶ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/blob/main/docs/developer/policy-engine.md>

²⁷ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/docs/blob/main/developer/handbook.md#policies>

²⁸ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/blob/main/docs/developer/policy-engine.md#absolute-spatial-position-constraint-function>

²⁹ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/blob/main/docs/developer/policy-engine.md#partner-level-constraint-function>

³⁰ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/docs/blob/main/developer/handbook.md#contract-definitions>

³¹ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/tree/main/docs/developer/ids-dataspace-protocol#goals>

³² <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/blob/main/docs/developer/policy-engine.md#policy-scopes>

³³ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/docs/blob/main/developer/handbook.md#policy-scopes>

Scope	Description	Relevance
contract.negotiation	Evaluated upon initial contract offer. Ensures that the consumer fulfils the contract policy	Relevant for end users in every use case
transfer.process	Evaluated before starting a transfer process to ensure that the policy of the contract agreement is fulfilled. One example would be contract expiry.	Relevant for end users in every use case
catalog	Evaluated when the catalog for a particular participant agent is generated. Decides whether the participant has the asset in their catalog	Relevant for end users in every use case
request.contract.negotiation	Evaluated on every request during contract negotiation between two control plane runtimes	Not relevant for end users
request.contract.process	Evaluated on every request during transfer establishment between two control plane runtimes	Not relevant for end users
request.catalog	Evaluated upon an incoming catalog request	Not relevant for end users
provision.manifest.verify	Evaluated during the precondition check for resource provisioning	Only relevant in advanced use cases

Table 2. Policy enforcement contexts

Another way to understand policy scopes is for them to be the link between a rule and an evaluation function and the points in the code where it needs to be evaluated.

5.2.1.2 Policy Monitor

The Policy Monitor is an EDC connector module that allows for continuous enforcement of policies on running Transfer Processes. Unlike finite transfers, streaming flows need to be under continuous control to avoid unauthorised data usage and transfer.

The Policy Monitor is implemented as a state machine. When a provider transfer process starts, it loops continuously and evaluates the contract policy using the Policy Engine. If the Policy becomes invalid, the Policy Monitor automatically completes the transfer process.

5.2.2 Final Status

Based on the analysis of the current framework for the enforcement of the Policy Engine, several functions have been implemented³⁴. The policies have been classified according to the type of data required to check the constraint:

- Generic data: independent from the consumer characteristics.
- Static data: based on consumer information that do not change.
- Dynamic data based on context-specific information available only at runtime.

Within the extension of the Policy Engine integrated with the EDC connector, three policies have been developed:

- Time Interval Policy (generic information):
 - Grants access to data product only within a defined time window.

Figure 34 shows an example of a policy that allows access between two specific dates.

³⁴<https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/idsa-gaia-x-connectors-and-components/policy-engine-extension>

```

{
  "@context": {
    "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/"
  },
  "@id": "aPolicyTimeInterval",
  "@type": "edc:PolicyDefinition",
  "policy": {
    "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl.jsonld",
    "@type": "Set",
    "permission": [
      {
        "action": "use",
        "constraint": [
          {
            "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
            "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval",
            "rightOperand": {
              "@type": "xsd:date",
              "@value": "2022-12-31T23:00:00.000Z"
            }
          },
          {
            "operator": {
              "@id": "odrl:gteq"
            }
          }
        ]
      },
      {
        "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
        "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/timeInterval",
        "rightOperand": {
          "@type": "xsd:date",
          "@value": "2024-09-30T23:00:00.000Z"
        }
      },
      {
        "operator": {
          "@id": "odrl:lteq"
        }
      }
    ]
  }
},
  "prohibition": [],
  "obligation": []
}

```

Figure 34. Example of “time interval” policy

- Location Policy (static information):
 - Restricts access to consumers in a given geographic area.
 - Requires the provider connector to know the location of the consumer company.
 - This information is stored as an attribute in Keycloak.

Figure 35 shows an example of the Location Policy.

```

{
  "@context": {
    "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/"
  },
  "@id": "aPolicyRegion",
  "@type": "edc:PolicyDefinition",
  "policy": {
    "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl.jsonld",
    "@type": "Set",
    "permission": [
      {
        "action": "use",
        "constraint": {
          "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
          "leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/regionLocation",
          "operator": "odrl:eq",
          "rightOperand": "eu"
        }
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Figure 35. Example of “location” policy

- Purpose Policy (dynamic information):
 - Restricts access based on the declared purpose of use, or role-based attributes within the consumer organisation. The same consumer may retrieve the data product for different purposes or business units.

Figure 36 shows an example of a Purpose Policy.

```

{ "@context": {
  "@vocab": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/"
},
"@id": policy_id,
"@type": "edc:PolicyDefinition",

"policy": {
  "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl.jsonld",
  "@type": "Set",
  "permission": [
    {
      "action": "use",
      "constraint": {
        "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
        "odrl:leftOperand": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/purpose",
        "rightOperand": {
          "@type": "xsd:string",
          "@value": marketing
        },
        "operator": {
          "@id": "odrl:eq"
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}
}

```

Figure 36. Example of “purpose” policy

Initially, Location and Purpose Policies supported only the ODRL eq and neq operators, allowing equality and inequality checks. New logical ODRL operators have been added for use, including: hasPart, isNoneOf, isPartOf, and isAnyOf.

The definition of both policies is as follows, and the allowed operators are highlighted in yellow in Figure 37.

```

{
  "@context":{
    "edc": "https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/"
  },
  "@id": "aPolicy",
  "@type": "edc:PolicyDefinition",
  "policy": {
    "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl.jsonld",
    "@type": "Set",
    "permission": [ {
      "action": "use",
      "constraint": {
        "@type": "AtomicConstraint",
        "odrl:leftOperand": https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/location |
https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/purpose ,
        "rightOperand": [{
          "@type": "xsd:string",
          "@value": "value1"
        }],
        "@type": "xsd:string",
        "@value": "value2"
      }
    }, ...],
    "operator": {
      "@id": "odrl:hasPart | odrl:isNoneOf | odrl:isPartOf | odrl:isAnyOf"
    }
  }
},
"prohibition": [],
"obligation": []
}

```

Figure 37. Example of “purpose” and “location” policy with new operators

In this exercise, the Policy Engine was successfully integrated into the deployment. For now, this deployment does not include Keycloak, needed for the purpose and location policies. Therefore, only the TimeInterval policy has been tested. For this test, an asset and a policy with a date range were created, along with a contract definition to enable catalog queries. Figure 38 shows the asset and the date range.

```

{
  "@id": "Y29udHJhY3QtZGVmaw5pdGlvbi10aw1l:YXNzZXRJZEVEQw==:NjYwZDE0MDgtOG",
  "@type": "odrl:Offer",
  "odrl:permission": {
    "odrl:action": {
      "@id": "odrl:use"
    },
    "odrl:constraint": [
      {
        "odrl:leftOperand": {
          "@id": "edc:timeInterval"
        },
        "odrl:operator": {
          "@id": "odrl:gteq"
        },
        "odrl:rightOperand": "2022-12-31T23:00:00.000Z"
      },
      {
        "odrl:leftOperand": {
          "@id": "edc:timeInterval"
        },
        "odrl:operator": {
          "@id": "odrl:lteq"
        },
        "odrl:rightOperand": "2025-12-30T23:00:00.000Z"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Figure 38. Example of fetching catalog from the EDC provider connector

During the negotiation phase and for policy testing, the end date of the interval was changed, as Figure 39 illustrates.

```

        xLWIwOGUtYjE1ZTFhNDM2MDgy",
        "@type": "odrl:Offer",
        "odrl:permission": {
            "odrl:action": {
                "@id": "odrl:use"
            },
            "odrl:constraint": [
                {
                    "odrl:leftOperand": {
                        "@id": "edc:timeInterval"
                    },
                    "odrl:operator": {
                        "@id": "odrl:gteq"
                    },
                    "odrl:rightOperand": "2022-12-31T23:00:00.000Z"
                },
                {
                    "odrl:leftOperand": {
                        "@id": "edc:timeInterval"
                    },
                    "odrl:operator": {
                        "@id": "odrl:lteq"
                    },
                    "odrl:rightOperand": "2026-12-30T23:00:00.000Z"
                }
            ]
        },
        "odrl:prohibition": [],
        "odrl:obligation": []
    }
}

```

Figure 39. Example of Negotiation of an Asset

This allows verification of the check between the policy and the contract, resulting in an error as shown in Figure 40.

```

ent
provider-controlplane | SEVERE 2025-07-16T09:59:05.16189963 ContractNegotiation: ID 3db436ef-b4a9-4983-b102-1b8aa6b686df. Fatal error while [Pr
ovider] send agreement. Error details: {"@type":"dSPACE:ContractNegotiationError","dSPACE:code":"400","dSPACE:reason":"Contract agreement received. Valid
ation failed: Policy in the contract agreement is not equal to the one in the contract offer","@context":{"dcat":"http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#","dct":"http
://purl.org/dc/terms/","odrl":"http://www.w3.org/ns/odrl/2/","dSPACE":"https://w3id.org/dSPACE/v0.8/","vocab":"https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/","edc":"h
ttps://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/"}}
provider-controlplane | DEBUG 2025-07-16T09:59:05.162224791 [ProviderContractNegotiationManagerImpl] ContractNegotiation 3db436ef-b4a9-4983-b10
2-1b8aa6b686df is now in state TERMINATED

```

Figure 40. Example of policy engine enforcement

The message in the figure indicates that the policy is not fulfilled, meaning no further steps can be taken to access the asset. In summary, the policy engine is operating correctly.

5.2.2.1 Open issues and lessons learnt

Currently, the policy engine provides only data access control and enforcement, but there are several challenges to be solved to provide data usage control functionality:

- **Semantic interoperability:** One important issue to be solved is ensuring interoperability when evaluating some constraint, for example, to map the allowed purposes with the purpose of the consumer.
- **Data usage enforcement:** An even greater challenge is how to ensure that the data is only used for a specific purpose or by a specific area in the consumer company, i.e., the data usage policy enforcement. The separation between the control and the transfer planes makes the enforcement more difficult, if not impossible unless the data is only used in a controlled environment.

The purpose and location policies remain to be tested once the EDC is integrated with Keycloak, since both policies require a source from which to retrieve information for validation. Initially, the EDC had this information hardcoded in its configuration file. The current approach is to retrieve it from Keycloak specifically from client attributes defined for each connector. A possible solution for the semantic interoperability is the use of Verifiable presentations (VPs) as a source of information for policy enforcement.

5.3 Logging Tool

The Logging Tool in Data Sharing and Sovereignty Mechanisms offers a robust solution for tracking, monitoring, and auditing data transactions. It ensures that all data interactions remain transparent, secure and aligned with applicable regulations and policies. By carefully logging actions and events within DATAMITE framework, the tool generates an immutable audit trail that supports data integrity and accountability. Integrating such a tool into data sharing and sovereignty strategies not only strengthens the reliability and secure of data exchanges but also helps organizations fulfil compliance requirements and uphold data sovereignty principles. It is a vital asset for any organization to enable data sharing while retaining full control over its data resources. Figure 41 depicts the Logging Tool within the DATAMITE's Architecture.

Figure 41. The Logging Tool within the DATAMITE’s Architecture

5.3.1 Design Overview

5.3.1.1 Scope

The scope of this tool is to monitor and audit data preparation and data exchanges by tracking all actions within the DATAMITE framework. It ensures transparency by maintaining an audit log of key interactions. The tool relies on DATAMITE’s data-sharing mechanisms, which underpin its functionality and enable secure and efficient data transactions. From a technical perspective, it is not an independent tool; rather, it retrieves and stores actions performed across several DATAMITE modules through service-to-service communication. The primary outcome of the tool is to provide comprehensive monitoring of all data-sharing transactions carried out via DATAMITE’s data product composition and data-sharing mechanisms. Consequently, the DATAMITE framework delivers detailed information regarding data management and access.

5.3.1.2 Workflow

Figure 42 depicts the workflow of the logging tool within the DATAMITE framework, illustrating the interactions with other components, such as Data Product Composition and Data Sharing Mechanisms (EDC, GAIA-X and EU Portals), and the user’s interaction. A user, through the front-end interface, prepares the data and metadata according to the desired data destination. The user then publishes the data to the chosen destination, following the processes supported by the data destination. The tool monitors the entire process, storing relevant information from the data preparation to the data publishing. Up to this stage, the communication is service-to-service, so

the user does not interact directly with the tool. Finally, through the front-end, the user can query the stored information, such as the history of a data product.

Figure 42. The workflow of the logging tool

5.3.2 Final Status

There has been a migration of the database from MySQL to PostgreSQL in order to adopt the DATAMITE framework.

Additional changes were implemented in alignment with the EDC connector for GAIA-X, as well as to support unified monitoring for EU brokers. A common structure has been followed across all the portals in order to ensure smooth compatibility and accurate logging. The payload of the endpoints that are responsible for publishing contains key information such as the platform, the

GET /publicationsLog/searchWithFilters Filters the publications logs by the below fields, empty the values from fields not desired, each filter is applied with and operator

Filters the publications logs by the below fields, empty the values from fields not desired, each filter is applied with and operator

Parameters
Cancel

Name	Description
Portal string <small>(query)</small>	Filters the publications logs by Portal (Portal = EDC, GaiaX, AloD, Zenodo, MISTRAL, PontusX) <input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="AloD"/>
dataProductId string <small>(query)</small>	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="bad443d1-48dd-4efe-986b-ef915cfe3294"/>
fromDate string <small>(query)</small>	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="2024-01-19T12:39:03.111Z"/>
toDate string <small>(query)</small>	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="2025-01-19T12:39:03.111Z"/>
authToken * required string <small>(header)</small>	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpzZW50L3plYXQ9LCJ0eXAiOiJKV1QiLCJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiJ9"/>

Execute

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	OK	No links

Media type

Controls Accept header.

Example Value | Schemas

```
[
  {
    "portal": "zenodo",
    "publicationid": "zenodoID",
    "dataProductId": "bad443d1-48dd-4efe-986b-ef915cfe3294",
    "username": "username",
    "timestamp": "2024-01-19T12:39:03.111Z",
    "action": "create",
    "hash": "example",
    "metadata": [
      {}
    ]
  },
  {
    "portal": "gaiax",
    "publicationid": "gaiaxid",
    "dataProductId": "the_internal_product_id",
    "username": "username",
    "timestamp": "2024-01-19T12:39:03.111Z",
    "action": "delete",
    "hash": "",
    "metadata": [
      {}
    ]
  }
]
```

Figure 44. Example for search with filters endpoint for publications page

Furthermore, the logging tool was integrated with the data product composition tool, enabling the tracking of all actions and processes associated with internal data products (Figure 45). By developing a series of query requests, users are able to search by dataProductId and/or portal and retrieve all the related actions and the history of the internal data products (Figure 46).

GET /dataProductLog/searchHistory Returns the history of a selected Data Product

Returns the history of a selected Data Product

Parameters Cancel

Name	Description
page <small>integer (query)</small>	<input style="width: 150px;" type="text" value="1"/>
limit <small>integer (query)</small>	<input style="width: 150px;" type="text" value="2"/>
authToken <small>* required</small> <small>string (header)</small>	<input style="width: 150px;" type="text" value="eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXLTUwIiwiaWF0Ijoi"/>

Execute

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	OK	<small>No links</small>

Media type

application/json

Controls Accept header.

Example Value | Schema

```

{
  "status": 200,
  "message": "success",
  "data": {
    "total": 10,
    "page": 1,
    "limit": 10,
    "results": [
      {
        "dataProductId": "350ba92e-7658-4816-b6f6-579529d1cc7f",
        "dataProductName": "weather_catalog",
        "isDeleted": true,
        "deletedBy": "Alice Brown",
        "deletedAt": "2024-01-19T12:39:03.111Z",
        "isAnonymized": true,
        "anonymization": [
          {
            "anonymizedBy": "Alice Brown",
            "anonymizedAt": "2024-01-19T12:39:03.111Z",
            "techniques": [
              "masking",
              "generalization"
            ],
            "columns": [
              "name",
              "age"
            ]
          }
        ],
        "privacy_models": [
          "k-anonymity"
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Figure 46. Data Product Composition searchHistory sample response

As referenced in 5.4.3 “Future Work” of deliverable D2.2, certain features related to Metadata Harvester Broker were proposed but not implemented, as described in Section 3.3.4.1.

For the authentication process, the tool retrieves the token on the headers provided by DATAMITE’s access control and integrates role-based access control (RBAC). Description for access control is available in WP3 deliverables.

The logging tool was integrated with the Front-End, receiving inputs from service-to-service communication. The users are also able to access the relevant information. The corresponding information is presented in Section 7 (User Interface for Data Sharing & Sovereignty).

Figure 47 depicts an example of the SWAGGER documentation for the available endpoints of the Logging Tool. These endpoints primarily support actions related to data product composition and the data retrieval on the Publications page. For data product composition endpoints, each user action is logged in the database through the corresponding endpoints. User can filter these entries to retrieve either specific logged actions or the complete history of a given data product. Similar, for the Publications section, after users publish their data via DATAMITE’s Data Sharing Mechanisms, relevant actions are also logged. Users can filter these entries in the same manner to access either the logged actions or the historical record of a data product. There is a corresponding repository³⁵ in Eclipse for more information about the logging tool.

Data Product Composition		Operations related to Data Product Composition	^
POST	/dataProductLog/create	To log information when a data product is created	∨
POST	/dataProductLog/update	To log information when a data product is updated	∨
POST	/dataProductLog/delete	To log information when a data product is deleted	∨
POST	/dataProductLog/updateMetadata	To log information when metadata are updated	∨
POST	/dataProductLog/anonymization	To log information when a data product is anonymized	∨
POST	/dataProductLog/download	To log information when a data product is downloaded	∨
GET	/dataProductLog/getall	Returns all the logs about Data Product composition actions	∨
GET	/dataProductLog/searchWithFilters	Filters the Data Product Composition logs by the below fields, empty the values from fields not desired, each filter is applied with and operator	∨
GET	/dataProductLog/searchHistory	Returns the history of a selected Data Product	∨
GET	/dataProductLog/searchHistoryWithFilters	Filters the history of Data Product Composition logs by the below fields, empty the values from fields not desired, each filter is applied with and operator	∨
Publications		Operations related to publications	^
GET	/publicationsLog/getall	Returns all the logs about publications	∨
GET	/publicationsLog/searchWithFilters	Filters the publications logs by the below fields, empty the values from fields not desired, each filter is applied with and operator	∨
GET	/publicationsLog/searchHistory	Returns the history of publications	∨
GET	/publicationsLog/searchHistoryWithFilters	Filters the publications history by the below fields, empty the values from fields not desired, each filter is applied with and operator	∨

Figure 47. SWAGGER Documentation for Logging tool

³⁵ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-sharing/logging-tool>

6 Evaluation Guidance for Data Sovereignty

6.1 State of the Art

The concept of data sovereignty has emerged as a critical issue in the context of digitalisation and cross-company data ecosystems. While organisations of all sizes increasingly rely on data-driven value creation, the ability to maintain control over data across its lifecycle remains a persistent challenge³⁶. Current approaches are fragmented, data ownership lacks a consistent legal definition in the European Union, and enforcement mechanisms for data-sharing agreements are often weak³⁷.

Frameworks such as the International Data Spaces (IDS) and GAIA-X provide initial foundations by defining certification schemes and policy standards. However, they do not yet establish robust enforcement instruments, leaving organisations uncertain about compliance and operationalisation³⁸. At the same time, the European legislative landscape, shaped by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the European Data Act³⁹, and the NIS2 Directive⁴⁰, sets ambitious requirements for secure, transparent, and fair data use. These regulations emphasise the rights of data subjects, the necessity of robust security measures, and the obligation to ensure lawful processing.

In practice, organisations face difficulties balancing regulatory compliance with technical feasibility. Challenges such as jurisdictional conflicts, insufficient transparency in data flows, and the lack of interoperable standards hinder implementation. Consequently, there is a critical need for structured evaluation models that allow organisations to measure their current level of maturity in implementing data sovereignty and to identify targeted areas for improvement.

³⁶ Hummel, Patrik; Braun, Matthias; Tretter, Max; Dabrock, Peter (2021): Data sovereignty: A review. In: Big Data & Society 8 (1), Article 2053951720982012, p. 1–17. DOI: 10.1177/2053951720982012.

³⁷ Hans Graux (2024): What is data ownership, and does it still matter under EU data law. In: data.europa.eu.

³⁸ Lohmöller, Johannes; Pennekamp, Jan; Matzutt, Roman; Schneider, Carolin Victoria; Vlad, Eduard; Trautwein, Christian; Wehrle, Klaus (2024): The unresolved need for dependable guarantees on security, sovereignty, and trust in data ecosystems. In: Data & Knowledge Engineering 151 (102301), p. 1–23. DOI: 10.1016/j.datak.2024.102301.

³⁹ https://www.eu-data-act.com/Data_Act_Articles.html

⁴⁰ https://www.nis-2-directive.com/NIS_2_Directive_Articles.html

6.2 Methodological Approach

An iterative, multi-step methodology was developed to construct a robust evaluation framework. The process began with an extensive exploration of the relevant literature, covering scientific publications, legal texts, and industry standards. This provided a theoretical and legal basis for identifying the initial set of criteria to be considered.

In the second step, semi-structured expert interviews were conducted across multiple sectors, including automotive, aerospace, and IT.

These interviews provide valuable insights into the practical application of data sovereignty principles, highlighting how organisations currently manage data sovereignty within their systems, the obstacles they face, and the specific requirements of different sectors. In addition, they provide an opportunity to identify and discuss the technical, legal, and organisational challenges faced by organisations in implementing data sovereignty measures.

The evaluation of data sovereignty within the organisations involved an examination of the six validated key criteria, based on the exploration of relevant literature and expert insights.

To assess the degree of implementation, a comprehensive questionnaire was developed, structured around the core dimensions of data sovereignty: ownership, supervision, locality, residency, security, and data protection. A Likert scale⁴¹, was used to evaluate the degree of implementation of each criterion. Based on their scores, organisations were categorised into three levels of maturity: Basic Implementation, Intermediate Development, and Full Integration.

6.3 Results

The questionnaire was distributed to a diverse set of organisations. The responses revealed a heterogeneous picture of implementation levels. Based on the responses, organisations were categorised into three levels of implementation as illustrated in Figure 48.

⁴¹ <https://forms.office.com/e/Unegs58DxA>

Figure 48. Visualisation of the Data Sovereignty Implementation Levels of the Participating Organisations

- **Basic Implementation (< 50 %):** Organisations are in the early stages of adopting data sovereignty practices or face major challenges. Key areas requiring attention include the reinforcement of governance frameworks, the enhancement of technical infrastructure, and the implementation of stronger security measures.
- **Intermediate Development (50–99 %):** Organisations demonstrate more consistent integration of sovereignty principles, but still require optimisation in areas such as cross-border compliance and continuous monitoring.
- **Full Integration (100 %):** Organisations have successfully embedded data sovereignty across all areas. The focus is on fine-tuning processes, ensuring continuous improvement, and maintaining strong alignment with regulatory and security requirements. DATAMITE supports these organisations in sustaining high standards while optimising data monetisation strategies.

Visualisations of the results presented in Figure 49 made it possible to distinguish strengths and weaknesses across the six criteria. Each criterion is analysed separately, providing a more

detailed view of how sovereignty principles are being applied in different domains. For instance, while most organisations had implemented baseline security measures, challenges persisted in ensuring data residency compliance and in translating abstract ownership concepts into enforceable policies.

Figure 49. Visualisations of the implementation levels for each criterion based on the responses to the questionnaire

6.4 Conclusion and Outlook

The evaluation model provides a scalable framework for organisations to self-assess their data sovereignty practices. It goes beyond compliance monitoring by offering a structured maturity classification: Basic Implementation, Intermediate Development, and Full Integration. This differentiation allows targeted recommendations, supporting organisations in aligning technical, organisational, and legal dimensions.

DATAMITE's technical modules, such as the Policy Engine, Policy Library, and Logging Tool, complement the evaluation by providing concrete instruments for policy enforcement, security, and transparency. The evaluation thus functions not only as a diagnostic tool but also as a roadmap for continuous improvement.

However, the current results are based on a limited number of responses. A future gap analysis, once more data is collected, will enhance the explanatory power of the framework. This will enable a more granular understanding of sector-specific challenges and guide the development of tailored interventions.

In conclusion, the research contributes to both academic and practical debates on data sovereignty. It integrates theoretical insights, legal frameworks, and empirical evidence into a coherent evaluation methodology. By operationalising complex regulatory and technical requirements into measurable criteria, the DATAMITE framework supports organisations in navigating the evolving European data economy while strengthening their sovereignty over digital assets.

7 User Interface for Data Sharing & Sovereignty

The DATAMITE framework supports a complete lifecycle for data products, guiding users through each stage with an integrated set of tools. The process begins with the listing of data products (Figure 50), catalogued and made visible within the platform’s repository. This catalogue acts as the entry point for both data providers and potential consumers, ensuring that all assets are clearly organised and easy to navigate.

Figure 50. Data Products listed

A data product can be created through the framework’s dedicated interface, where its structure is defined and key details are set. First, the user provides the name and description of the new data product (Figure 51). Next, artifacts can be selected from an existing dataset (Figure 52) or the user can choose from previously created data products (Figure 53). This approach allows for flexible creation, enabling users to build new products either from raw dataset components or by leveraging existing products, streamlining workflow and promoting reusability across projects.

Figure 51. First step of creating a Data Product

Figure 52. Available methods to create a Data Product: Select artifacts from the Datasets or select Data Products

Figure 53. Available methods to create a Data Product: Select artifacts from the Datasets or select Data Products

The next step is the completion of metadata (Figure 54 and Figure 55) in which users provide descriptive information, categorisations, and technical details. This ensures that the data product is discoverable and understandable, supporting interoperability and reusability. The user can also update the data product content by aggregating rows and columns (Figure 56), delete or retain columns (Figure 57), composite data products (Figure 58) and filter by specific criteria (Figure 59).

Figure 54. Metadata completion in the DATAMITE Framework

Publisher	Size	Modified	
DATAMITE	2993		
Aggregation Of	Compliant To	Domains	Keywords
	EDC	string	string
Languages	Policies	Relevant to	
string	string	string	

License	Terms and Conditions	Spatial Coverage	Temporal Coverage
Not defined	Not defined	Not defined	Not defined

Distribution
Not defined

Figure 55. Metadata completion in the DATAMITE Framework

Figure 56. Updating a Data Product: Aggregate by columns or rows

Figure 57. Updating a Data Product: Delete and Retain Columns

Figure 58. Updating a Data Product: Aggregate and Composite

Figure 59. Updating a Data Product: Filtering

When ready, the data product can be published simultaneously to multiple European data portals through the framework’s publishing service (Figure 60). Each successful release automatically generates a publication record, formalising the availability of the dataset and making it visible to external audiences.

Figure 60. Publishing a data product to multiple European portals

Publish a Data Product

1 Token

2 Publication

3 Distribution

4 Policy

1 Token

Insert the authentication token of the EU Portal.

1. Token

Next

Figure 61. Providing an access token for portal authentication

In some cases, certain portals may require the provision of an access token (Figure 61). The publication also requires the definition of general information such as a description (Figure 62) and also the completion of the distribution metadata (Figure 63). The creation of specific data access policies (Figure 64) before the publication can proceed can also be needed for some EU portals, such as the EDC portal.

Publish a Data Product

1 Token

2 Publication

3 Distribution

4 Policy

2 Publication

Once confirmed, your data product will be published and accessible as specified.

4. Publication

Description

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Name

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Back

Next

Figure 62. Entering general data product information

Publish a Data Product

- 1 Token
- 2 Publication
- 3 Distribution
- 4 Policy

3. Distribution

Review the existing distribution settings and make any changes if needed before publishing.

3. Item 1

Checksum

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Checksum_algorithm

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Back Next

Figure 63. Completing the distribution metadata of the data product

Publish a Data Product

- 1 Token
- 2 Publication
- 3 Distribution
- 4 Policy

4. Policy

Begin by setting the foundation of your policy.

5. Legal Registration Type

TimeInterval Policy

Create Policy

Back Publish

Figure 64. Defining data access policies before publication

Then, when the publication is completed, the framework shows a listing of the data products published in several EU portals (Figure 65) and it also has a detail page for each one with general information of the specific publication (Figure 66).

Figure 65. Listing published data products across EU portals

Figure 66. Viewing detailed information for a published data product

Figure 67. Tracking data product history logs

Finally, the framework maintains comprehensive history logs for both data products (Figure 67) and their publications (Figure 68), capturing every change, update, and republication. This ensures full traceability, transparency, and accountability across the entire data-sharing process.

Figure 68. Tracking publication history logs

8 Conclusions

This document has presented the final release of the data sharing and data sovereignty mechanisms within the DATAMITE framework, detailing the adopted technologies and the developed components. It outlines the design, functionalities, and integration of the various components within the WP2-related modules and provides links to the Eclipse Repository hosting the development efforts, where relevant. More specifically, it analyses the IDSA and GAIA-X connectors and components, which enable the integration of the framework with IDSA dataspace environments, as well as the brokers that facilitate data sharing with EU Portals and Data Markets. Furthermore, it describes the processes for preparing and managing data and metadata to enhance interoperability. Finally, it highlights the sovereignty aspects of data and the transparency features of the DATAMITE framework.

Appendix C: Data product concept analysis

In the context of data spaces, the concept of “data product” is being used and defined in several initiatives and standards, but still, there is no consensus about its meaning.

For example, the current version of the DSSC Blueprint⁴² states:

“The term ‘data product’ is highly conflated, meaning that two or more concepts or ideas are being mixed up, combined, or treated as if they were the same. This usually occurs when differences between the concepts are overlooked or misunderstood, resulting in a blending of meanings that can obscure the nuances and specifics of each concept. Conflation typically leads to confusion in discussions, analysis, and decision-making, especially in complex fields where precise terminology is crucial.”

In this Appendix, some of the definitions of the “data product” concept are presented and compared. Finally, the current “data product” approach in Gaia-X is analysed, specifically from the on-boarding process point of view.

The following sources have been included in the analysis.

- DSSC: Blueprint 1.5 (work in progress).
- IDS data product included in the Data Space protocol specification.
- DCAT 3.0 and ODRL.
- GAIA-X Trust Framework and Architecture.

The analysis is based on information taken from the sources, and it must be taken into account that they are evolving at a very high pace in some cases, or it is only preliminary work. The analysis tries to highlight the more stable results and common findings.

C.1 DSSC Data product concept

The DSSC glossary includes the “Data product” concept, but it distinguishes between two different views: the Business Data product and the Technical Data product.

⁴²<https://dataspacesupportcentre.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/BV15/pages/367527403/Conceptual+Model+-+Data+Products+and+Offerings#Purpose>

The technical data product is defined as “a set of **data services**, **data sets** and or other **resources**” that can be requested by a participant agent of a data product customer and provided by a participant agent of the data product owner”. Furthermore, the concept of “technical data product contract” represented by an **ODRL**⁴³ **policy** is used to define the access control policies for the data provider and the data usage policies for the data consumers.

The DSSC conceptual model also defines a possible mapping between the DSSC data product and the DCAT 3.0 standard:

- *A technical data product description is typically represented as a DCAT catalog object.*
- *A technical data product consists of DCAT resources, such as DCAT data sets, DCAT data services, and other (custom) subclasses of DCAT resources. The DCAT catalog, which represents the technical data product description, contains all of them.*
- *Policies, including contracts, are represented as ODRL policies. Where appropriate, such policies are also contained in the DCAT catalog, which represents the technical data product description.*

Figure shows the current state of the conceptual model diagram for data products and data product offerings being developed by the DSSC in the context of the development of the new version of its blueprint.

⁴³ ODRL Vocabulary & Expression 2.2 (w3.org)

Figure 69. Conceptual model diagram for data products and data product offerings (Source: DSSC)

The model includes the business data product, which adds to the technical view of the business perspective, including a variety of support processes, the specification of the data product offerings and contract templates.

C.2 IDSA Data Space protocol specification

The data space protocol does not define an explicit “data product” definition, and it maps the data offered by a participant agent to the Resource concept, which includes the Dataset and Data service concepts.

However, it differs from the DSSC Data product concept, a DSSC Data product corresponds to several IDSA Data services. Figure shows both data product views.

Figure 70. DSSC and IDSA data product comparison

C.3 GAIA-X

There are several working groups in Gaia-X defining the data product and other related models from different perspectives. The Trust Framework, WG Data Exchange Services, WG Architecture and WG Service Characteristics. Figure shows the Data product conceptual model in Gaia-X.

Figure 71. Data Product conceptual model (Source: Gaia-X Architecture Document - 23.10 Release)

C.4 DCAT data product related concepts.

A **dataset** in DCAT⁴⁴ is defined as a "collection of data, published or curated by a single agent, and available for access or download in one or more serializations or formats".

According to the DCAT specification, a dataset is a conceptual entity that can be represented by one or more **distributions** that serialize the dataset for transfer and distributions of a dataset can be provided via **data services**.

A **data service** is a more complex concept that can include selection, extraction, combination, processing or transformation operations over datasets, and it can correspond to the Data product concept in Gaia-X.

⁴⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

The result of any request to a data service is a representation of a part or all of a dataset or catalog. A data service might be tied to specific datasets, or its source data might be configured at request- or run-time. A data distribution service allows selection and download of a distribution of a dataset or subset.

C.5 DATAMITE particularisation of Gaia-X data product concept

In Figure , the complete DATAMITE data product Verifiable Presentation (VP) is shown. A Verifiable Presentation (VP) expresses data from one or more Verifiable Credentials (VC) that are digital credentials that adhere to relevant World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) open standards.

Figure 72. DATAMITE Data Product verifiable presentation conceptual map

According to the above figure, the Legal Participant's verifiable presentation is also included in the Data Product VP. **DATAMITE Gaia-X onboarding process** offers the complete API for creating it.

Table 3 and Table 4 show the information needed for a minimum participant and data product description. The current version assumes that the data product is accessed via a public API.

Properties	Value	Example
participantURL	URL of the participant self-descriptor	"https://DATAMITE.digital.tecnalia.dev/.well-known/participant.json"
domain	domain of the DNS	"DATAMITE.digital.tecnalia.dev"
legalName	Legal Name of the company	TECNALIA
headquarterAddress	Each pilot country code (Country-code in ISO 3166-2)	"ES-PV",
legalAddress	Each pilot country code (Country-code in ISO 3166-2)	"ES-PV",
legalRegistrationType	vatID, leiCode...	"vatID"
legalRegistrationNumber	vatID of the Company (G45XXXX)	"G48975XX"

Table 3. Gaia-X Participant data model

Properties	Value	Example
participantURL	URL of the participant self-descriptor	"https://DATAMITE.digital.tecnalia.dev/.well-known/participant.json"
domain	Domain	"DATAMITE.digital.tecnalia.dev"
dataProductName	Name for the data product	"Dataproduct example",
dataProductDesc	Data product description	"Description of data product",
dataProductTC	A resolvable link to the Terms and Conditions applying to that service.	"https://aws.amazon.com/service-terms/",
dataProductPolicy	Policy in ODRL format	"default:allow"
dataAccount:requestType	Allowed values: API , email, webform, unregisteredLetter, registeredLetter, supportCenter	"API"

Properties	Value	Example
dataAccount:accessType	Allowed values: digital , physical	“digital”
dataAccount:formatType	Type of media Types: application/json, text/plain	"application/vnd.ms-excel"
Host (serviceAccessPointInfo)	host of the endpoint	"dataestur.azure-api.net"
Port (serviceAccessPointInfo)	port of the endpoint	"443"
Protocol (serviceAccessPointInfo)	protocol of the endpoint	"https"
Version (serviceAccessPointInfo)	version of the endpoint	"1.0.0"
openAPIURL (serviceAccessPointInfo)	URL of the API/REST	"https://dataestur.azure-api.net/API-SEGITTUR-v1/ACTIVIDADES_OCIO_DL?CCAA=Todos&Provincia=Todos"
name	Data resource name	"dataresource1"
description	Data resource description	"description 1"
license	An identifier or URL to document. https://github.com/spdx/license-list-data/tree/main/jsonld	"EPL-2.0"
copyrightOwnedBy	Owner of the data resource	"original owner"

Table 4. Gaia-X “data product” model

C.6 Challenges and open issues

Data product multi data set view does not correspond with the current connectors asset concept. The concept of “data product” as the result of the application of an algorithm to a dataset using a cloud infrastructure, promoted by Gaia-X and focused in getting value from data based on specific uses cases does not fit well with data sharing scenarios where the data is not provided with a

specific goal in advance but to facilitate the free flow of data as it is being promoted by the European Data Strategy.